

ATLANTIC SALMON & SHAD STOCKING OPERATIONS: identified challenges, historical and contemporary strategies, and guidelines

Literature Review of Stocking Programs for Atlantic Salmon and Shad Species

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FOREWORD

The objective of this document is to provide a comprehensive synthesis of current knowledge regarding conservation-oriented stocking programs for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and shads (*Alosa spp.*). To ensure scientific rigor and reliability of the presented information, this synthesis relies exclusively on peer-reviewed scientific literature published in academic journals and data validated through peer review processes.

While based on findings from various stocking programs, this work specifically aims to inform discussions on **conservation-oriented stocking programs**. The analyses, interpretations, and recommendations derived from this work are therefore inherently tied to this conservation objective. It is crucial to note that certain considerations may be less relevant—or even inappropriate—in the context of fisheries-support stocking programs.

REVIEW

This document was collectively reviewed as part of an intellectual service provided by SCIMABIO Interface, with the participation of members of the project steering committee: L. Beaulaton (OFB), A. Caudron (SCIMABIO Interface), M. Chanseau (OFB), M. Motte (INRAe), C. Pénil (OFB), C. Garnier (DGALN), B. Valadou (OFB), L. Wendling (DGAMPA), and J. Wizniak (DGALN). Participation in the review does not necessarily imply agreement with all of the conclusions and analyses in this work, which remain the sole responsibility of their authors.

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PART I

Introduction and systematic review

ATLANTIC SALMON

Salmo salar

Introduction

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1.1. OVERALL CONTEXT

Each year, several million Atlantic salmon juveniles are released into European rivers through stocking programs, representing one of the largest and most expensive conservation and fisheries management efforts in the world. Yet despite this massive investment, the long-term ecological, genetic, and socio-economic outcomes of salmon stocking remain highly contested (McMillan et al. 2023, NASCO 2024, Ritter 1997), with concerns ranging from low adult return rates and genetic erosion or maladaptation (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Fraser 2008, Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007, McMillan et al. 2023, Naish et al. 2007, Ritter 1997) to unintended ecosystem effects (Castillo et al. 2008, Molony et al. 2003, Ritter 1997) and questionable economic efficiency (Harrison et al. 2018, Horreo et al. 2012, Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013).

The Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) is not only an ecological keystone species but also a cultural and economic emblem across Europe and North America. Once widespread across more than 2,000 rivers (Aas et al. 2011, ICES 2024), salmon populations have suffered severe declines over the past century, primarily due to overfishing, pollution, climate change, habitat fragmentation and dams that block upstream migration (Aas et al. 2011, NASCO 2019; 2024). In 2019, of the 2,356 rivers historically inhabited by Atlantic salmon, 43% are currently considered at risk (NASCO 2019)¹. In response, managers have turned to stocking - defined as “**the deliberate release of hatchery-reared fish into the wild at any stage of its life cycle for any purpose**” (NASCO 2024) - as a key intervention to support conservation, mitigate anthropogenic impacts, and sustain fisheries.

While other salmonid are stocked for divergent purposes (Aas et al. 2018, Naish et al. 2007), stocking for Atlantic salmon was first implemented as a political response to declining catches, rather than as a proper science-based conservation tool (Naish et al. 2007). Over time, its goals have diversified and now encompass harvest augmentation, supplementation of declining wild stocks, and

¹NASCO Atlantic salmon atlas

captive breeding for conservation (Fraser 2008, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Trushenski et al. 2015). In Europe, the term “conservation stocking” is often used to reflect a biodiversity focus (Bacon et al. 2015), whereas Scandinavian and North American programs more commonly emphasize “enhancement” or “supportive breeding” (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Salminen et al. 2007, Zink et al. 2023). Recent commentaries have raised critical questions about the ecological and ethical dimensions of these practices, including concerns about their naturalness and long-term sustainability (Harrison and Berseth 2024). Such comments and questions about the pertinence of stocking programs have been already raised in mid-20s (Vibert 1945). For instance, the International Congress for the Exploration of the Sea in 1933 raised the question to know whether the “salmon population can be improved only, or mainly, by the artificial propagation and whether the cost of such an operation corresponds to the results”.

Atlantic salmon is an ideal model to examine stocking impacts because of its complex anadromous life cycle, high site fidelity (i.e., homing), sensitivity to environmental change, and substantial socio-economic importance. In several European regions, including France, wild salmon populations are endangered or functionally extinct, raising the stakes for effective management. Despite decades of hatchery releases, evidence of sustained demographic recovery is often weak or absent, highlighting the need for more rigorous evaluation and adaptive management. Short-term gains in parr density or smolt output can be offset by domestication selection, loss of local genetic adaptations, altered behaviour and density-dependent competition with wild conspecifics. At the same time, managers are increasingly required — under the EU Water Framework Directive, Marine Strategy Framework Directive and the French *Plan saumon* (i.e., salmon plan) — to justify interventions with measurable indicators and to demonstrate that stocking is deployed only after avoidance and reduction measures have been fully explored (ERC sequence in French for Eviter, Reduire, Compenser; i.e.: Avoid, Reduce, Compensate). Moreover, the national plan for migratory amphihaline fish (PNMA) aims to define a decision-making framework for stocking programs.

Like Atlantic salmon, historic programs in France may have targeted shad. While these species share common life history traits with salmon, the definitions, methods, and results of stocking programs may differ. However, fewer studies monitored stocking programs involving shads, particularly Allis shad, and investigated the potential effects of such programs on populations. The main reason for this lack is notably the much lower number of such stocking programs compared to salmon, whatever the species. Therefore, it's important to provide knowledge and recommendations for these species and the stocking plans that would target them. This can be based on the literature available on salmon.

11.2. BACKGROUND TO THE SPECIES AND NATIONAL PLANS IN FRANCE

The three species targeted by this work, Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*, Figure 1.1), Allis shad (*Alosa alosa*, Figure 1.1), and twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*, Figure 1.1), are amphihaline migratory species, and this work is part of a continuous effort to develop ecosystem-based actions and recommendations for amphihaline migratory fish in France.

The Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), the allis shad (*Alosa alosa*), and the twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*) are three amphihaline migratory species found within the national French territory. In France, pop-

(a) Adults of Atlantic salmon *Salmo salar*. ©C.Bouchard

(b) Allis shad *Alosa alosa* released in the river Nivelle (64, France). ©INRAe/S.Glise

(c) Twaite shad *Alosa fallax* at a fish-trap. ©SCIMABIO Interface

Figure 1.1: Pictures of the three species

ulations of these three species are monitored using various methods and with varying observational intensity. In particular, these species are monitored at several STACOMI stations (fish migration monitoring stations). For shad species, reproductive monitoring — especially due to their distinctive spawning behavior (i.e., bulling) — serves as an indicator of population status, although the reliability of this estimate remains debated (Azam et al. 2020, Tentelier et al. 2021). In contrast, population monitoring is far more developed for Atlantic salmon. In addition to counting upstream-migrating spawners via video or capture at STACOMI stations, Index of Abundance (IA) monitoring fisheries targeting juveniles are conducted at various index sites (Azam et al. 2020, Brun et al. 2011, Prévost et al. 1996, Prévost and Nihouarn 1999).

Although all three species share an amphihaline life cycle — migrating between ocean and river environments — they exhibit substantial ecological and biological differences. These include variation in habitat use during both growth and reproductive phases, migratory behaviors, and associated phenology. Consequently, while these species are subject to similar anthropogenic pressures, they display diverse life-history traits and conservation challenges specific to each species.

All three species have exhibited stagnant or declining demographic trends at low population levels for several decades (André et al. 2021; 2018, Aprahamian et al. 2003, Baglinière et al. 2003, Legrand et al. 2020, Nachón et al. 2016). These negative dynamics are not limited to French river populations, but are also observed throughout the species' broader distribution ranges (Aprahamian et al. 2003, Baglinière et al. 2003, Nachón et al. 2016). However, regional differences exist between populations and river basins in France (Legrand et al. 2020).

Allis shad

Allis shad populations are exclusively found along the Atlantic coast and in the English Channel (Figure 1.2). Historically abundant populations have undergone the most dramatic percentage declines in abundance (Figure 1.3; André et al. 2018, Legrand et al. 2020) like in other countries (Limburg and Waldman 2009). In contrast, some small populations, such as those in the Charente River (Charente et al. 2023) and the Nivelle River (pers. comm., 2024), have shown stable or even increasing trends over the past five years. The species is currently listed as **Critically Endangered** on the French Red List of Threatened Freshwater Fish (UICN Comité Français and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle 2019). While no dedicated studies have been conducted in France, the species is believed to

exhibit homing behavior, with individuals tending to return to their natal river or at least to their natal catchment for reproduction (Jolly et al. 2012). This homing behavior leads to local adaptation (see Glossary III.i, page 66) and genetic differentiation among populations (Jolly et al. 2012). Numerous introductions and stocking operations have also produced results demonstrating this local adaptation (Hutchings 2014). Nonetheless, gene flow among neighboring populations is thought to occur, with some individuals migrating to non-natal rivers, resulting in low levels of genetic differentiation (Martin et al. 2015, Randon et al. 2018, Rougemont et al. 2022). Some interconnected populations likely function as metapopulations, with source–sink dynamics and interpopulation dispersal (Randon et al. 2018).

Twaite shad

Twaite shad is distributed along all three French maritime coasts: the English Channel, the Atlantic Ocean, and the Mediterranean Sea (Figure 1.2). This name includes both the Atlantic (*Alosa fallax*) and Mediterranean (*Alosa agone*) forms. Like allis shad, the species is listed on the French IUCN Red List of Threatened Freshwater Fish (UICN Comité Français and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle 2019), but with a **Near Threatened** status. Homing behavior has been demonstrated in British populations (Jolly et al. 2012), contributing to genetic differentiation among populations. However, in contrast to allis shad, this homing behavior appears to occur at the level of large catchments rather than at the level of specific rivers or local populations (Rougemont et al. 2022).

Atlantic salmon

A similar pattern of declining yet persistent small populations is also observed for Atlantic salmon in France. Among the three species studied in this project, Atlantic salmon is by far the most thoroughly researched — both globally and within French river systems. Some French populations are now reduced to just a few dozen individuals, while others comprise several hundred. Thanks to improved access to spawning grounds (e.g., dam removals), the present-day spatial distribution of the species in France resembles its historical 19th-century range, which had mostly disappeared by the 20th century (André et al. 2021, Thibault 1994, Figure 1.4). However, current population abundances remain far below historical levels. Atlantic salmon is characterized by strong homing behavior, with about 80% of spawners returning to their natal population (Hendry et al. 2004, Jonsson et al. 2003, Salmenkova 2017). The remaining 20%, considered dispersers, facilitate gene flow between populations if they successfully reproduce. This phenomenon is observed among certain Breton populations, which function as a metapopulation with source and sink dynamics, gene flow (Perrier et al. 2013b), and synchronized recruitment dynamics (Bouchard et al. 2022a). As such, during stocking efforts, juvenile fish released in one river may later migrate and spawn in another (Lange et al. 2015). While the species is widespread and abundant internationally, it is listed as **Near Threatened** on the French Red List due to the observed negative trends in many populations (UICN Comité Français and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle 2019).

Figure 1.2: Distribution of allis and twaite shad in French river systems. Figure from André et al. (2018).

Figure 1.3: Upstream migration counts of allis shad since 2002 at rivers equipped with monitoring stations. ©STACOMI. Figure from André et al. (2018).

Figure 1.4: Contemporary distribution (2007–2020) of Atlantic salmon in France. Figure from André et al. (2021).

// 1.2.1 GOVERNANCE AND MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

In metropolitan France, migratory fish are targeted by the National Plan for Amphihaline Migratory Species (PNMA), which complements basin-specific PLAGEPOMI plans (Plans for the Management of Migratory Fish), developed by the COGEPOMI (Migratory Fish Management Committees). Depending on basin characteristics and population status, each PLAGEPOMI outlines management and conservation measures focused on several major issues: biodiversity conservation, economic value, and fisheries management. These plans respond to and incorporate objectives from national and EU legislation, including:

- the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC),
- the EU Habitats Directive (92/43/EEC),
- the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC),
- the French Water and Aquatic Environments Law (LEMA, 2006-1772),
- the National Biodiversity Strategy (SNB),
- and national species-specific conservation plans.

The French salmon plan also incorporates recommendations from the North Atlantic Salmon Conservation Organization (NASCO, known as OSCAN in French).

In this complex management context, the French Biodiversity Office (OFB), in collaboration with INRAE, l'Institut Agro, and the University of Pau and the Adour Region (UPPA), coordinates the *MIAME R&D center* (Research and Development for Amphihaline Migratory Species in Their Environment). This group supports research, expert assessment, and management tools for amphihaline species and their ecosystems. It also publishes regular syntheses of population status in France (André et al. 2021; 2018).

// 1.2.2 OVERALL THREATS ON SALMON POPULATIONS

Atlantic salmon stocks are experiencing a widespread decline, characterized by a decrease in the abundance of returning adults and a reduction in adult body size (Dadswell et al. 2022), both of which adversely affect female fecundity. Between 1971 and 2009, the median estimated pre-fisheries abundance (PFA) of multiple sea-winter (MSW, see Glossary I.i, page 24) salmon declined by 54% in the North-Northeast Atlantic (N-NEAC) and by 81% in the South-Northeast Atlantic (S-NEAC, Chaput (2012)). For one-sea-winter (1SW, see Glossary I.i, page 24) individuals, the decline was less steady than for MSW salmon but still reached 49% in the N-NEAC and 66% in the S-NEAC (Chaput 2012).

Recent publications, such as Dadswell et al. (2022) and Thorstad et al. (2021), have reviewed the causes of global salmon declines and the potential stressors involved. Prior to the 1990s, the most significant factors included dams and habitat fragmentation, water pollution, and over-exploitation of

stocks (Dadswell et al. 2022, Thorstad et al. 2021). More recently, the expansion of salmon aquaculture has been shown to negatively impact wild stocks through the spread of salmon lice and genetic introgression from escaped farmed fish (Dadswell et al. 2022). While these threats are well-identified and can be directly addressed by managers, stakeholders, and policymakers, their mitigation remains a challenge (Thorstad et al. 2021) and the major threats on populations may vary regionally (Lennox et al. 2021).

Recent studies have also identified a general decline in marine survival rates across most stocks (Olmos et al. 2020). This synchronous reduction in sea survival suggests the influence of marine stressors, such as illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, as well as climate change, which increases sea temperatures and reduces food availability for salmon (Dadswell et al. 2022, ICES 2020, Olmos et al. 2020, Thorstad et al. 2021). Unlike freshwater threats, marine stressors are more difficult to mitigate, and populations with reduced genetic and phenotypic diversity may be less resilient to these challenges.

A key factor in understanding the demographic decline of French salmon populations is their location at the southern edge of the species' distribution range. These populations are exposed to higher river temperatures, leading to accelerated life cycles, and must migrate longer distances to reach marine feeding grounds. Most French stocks exhibit a decrease in average adult body size and weight, as well as a reduced proportion of MSW salmon among returning adults (André et al. 2021). Despite some spatial synchrony in juvenile abundances among geographically close populations (Bouchard et al. 2022a), most French populations are genetically distinct (Perrier et al. 2014). As such, they must be considered discrete and unique conservation units, although gene flow does occur through adult dispersal.

Although some adults disperse among populations (see “Dispersal” in Glossary I.i, page 24) and certain stressors synchronize population trends, evidence from introductions and stocking demonstrates strong local adaptation in salmonids (Hutchings 2014). This means that even geographically proximate populations may be genetically distinct and exhibit divergent behaviors. For example, the Allier population in France is one of the few populations in the country that pauses its migration during the summer, a unique adaptation to the long distances these adults must travel.

In these southern populations, parr (juvenile salmon) may become sexually mature before migrating to sea. The proportion of early-maturing individuals is typically higher in southern than in northern populations. Although these individuals do not experience the marine environment, they contribute to a higher effective number of breeders during reproduction, potentially increasing genetic diversity (Bacles et al. 2018, Saura et al. 2008, Valiente et al. 2005). The local adaptation of these populations is therefore crucial for their persistence and resilience.

Altogether, genetic diversity within and among populations — even those that are geographically close — is a crucial source of local adaptation that must be preserved. The diversity of life-history traits and behaviors, including the contribution of early-maturing individuals to reproduction, provides an important reservoir of adaptive potential for all French populations and should be carefully maintained.

GLOSSARY I.i: Salmon life cycle & life history

- YOY** Young-of-the-year salmon; individuals in their first year of life.
- Parr** Juvenile salmon in their second (1+) or third (2+) year in French populations.
- Smolt** Juvenile salmon preparing for their downstream migration to the sea, typically during their second (1+) or third (2+) year in French populations.
- 1SW** One Sea Winter salmon; individuals that spend only one winter at sea before returning to rivers to spawn.
- MSW** Multiple Sea Winter salmon; individuals that spend more than one winter at sea before returning to rivers to spawn.
- Anadromous** Refers to individuals that migrate from freshwater to the sea and return to freshwater to spawn (as opposed to precocious parr).
- Precocious parr** Early-maturing males that become sexually mature and reproduce in freshwater without migrating to sea.
- Downstream migration** The migration of smolts from their natal river to the sea.
- Upstream migration** The migration of anadromous adults from the sea back to freshwater rivers to spawn.
- Dispersal** The movement of an adult salmon from its natal river to another river.
- Gene flow** The transfer of genetic material that occurs when an adult salmon disperses to another river and successfully reproduces, contributing to the next generation in that river.
- Population** (or Local population) For salmon, a population is typically defined as the group of individuals inhabiting a specific river.
- Metapopulation** A group of populations that are connected by gene flow, such as the salmon metapopulation in Brittany (see Perrier et al. 2014).

1.3. AIMS OF THE REVIEW AND OVERALL METHOD

// 1.3.1 AIMS

This work contributes to an assessment of the scientific knowledge available and the historical and ongoing actions in France regarding fish stocking Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), Allis shad (*Alosa alosa*), and twaite shad (*Alosa fallax*) in France. While some studies and recent reviews have explored the benefits and effects of stocking programs, we aim to review stocking programs from a conservation perspective. This review aims to clarify the various types of stocking programs and their implications for monitoring and evaluating them. Additionally, we will identify design-efficient programs, assess their potential positive or negative outcomes, and outline methods for evaluating such programs. Here, we adopt a broad definition of “stocking” throughout, while retaining specific terms such as *enhancement*, *supplementation*, *conservation stocking*, and *supportive breeding* when authors use them to denote distinct management objectives or when we want to clearly discuss one type of stocking. All these terms and the associated differences in terms of stocking program objectives will be reviewed. This review aims to:

- i.* provide a comprehensive definition of the various types of “stocking”;
- ii.* summarize the historical development and current applications of stocking in Atlantic salmon;
- iii.* review the comparative biology between wild salmon and hatchery-reared salmon;
- iv.* assess ecological, phenotypic, sanitary, genetic, and socio-economic impacts reported in the literature;
- v.* review historical stocking programs to understand their causes of success and failures;
- vi.* review the already proposed evidence-based recommendations for improving management practices.

After a systematic review, the comprehensive review is structured into three main parts: Part II clarifies definitions, the different types of stocking and historical context (page 35); Part III reviews known effects of stocking programs (page 49); Part IV examines monitoring strategies, socio-economic integration, and policy recommendations (page 99). Behind the overall aims, the objectives of this review are:

- Summarize the evidence on the biological and ecological outcomes of salmon stocking programs conducted in France.
- Examine the decision framework that triggers stocking compared with alternative restoration tools.
- Identify indicators, knowledge gaps, and methodological obstacles that limit robust evaluation.
- Provide recommendations for integrating stocking operations into basin-scale adaptive management plans.

// 1.3.2 OVERALL METHOD

The review is based on a systematic Web of Science query, complemented by the screening of grey literature, such as management reports (COGEPOMI, water agency dossiers), expert consultation, and a comprehensive review. The comprehensive review involved searching for references that provided information, knowledge, and results on the various aims outlined earlier. While some references on other species or countries may offer valuable and pertinent results or knowledge, they may not be specific to salmon and may not be recent. Moreover, numerous programs have been conducted in other countries, providing valuable knowledge. Therefore, references are not limited to French programs. The systematic review is presented in the next chapter, while the rest of this document corresponds to the comprehensive review.

At the end of this review, a specific chapter is dedicated to the review for shad. Indeed, some stocking programs targeted shad (*Alosa alosa* and *Alosa fallax*) in France since French shad populations, like other French migratory fish populations, are in decline. However, since the literature

on shad is less dense and extensive compared to Atlantic salmon, an extensive review of salmon was conducted as a base for shad. This review was then supplemented with results and knowledge specific to shad, highlighting any potential differences between shad and salmon.

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CHAPTER **2**

Interface
University conservation

Systematic review

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2.1. QUERY AND SELECTION

While we initially conducted the comprehensive review by searching for specific references to address our *a priori* defined questions, the systematic review allowed us to provide a broader context of the scientific literature and to identify additional references that complemented the comprehensive review.

// 2.1.1 QUERY

We conducted a search of the Web of Science™ database on March 5th, 2025. Our query targeted the “topic” fields, specifically the title, abstract, and keywords. Any publication containing these terms in any of these fields was included in the results. The search criteria required the presence of either “Atlantic salmon” or “*Salmo salar*”, in combination with one or more of the following terms: “stocking”, “supplementation”, or “supportive breeding”. These terms were selected as they are the most commonly used in studies concerning salmon stocking. This search yielded 2,579 publications, which have been cited by a total of 42,141 other publications.

// 2.1.2 SELECTION

To further refine our search, we restricted the results to publications written in either French or English and published within the last 20 years (since 2005). We also limited the selection to articles, review articles, and early access articles, thereby excluding corrections, proceedings, book chapters, editorial materials, and meeting abstracts. After applying these criteria, the final selection comprised 2,066 publications.

Next, we extracted the titles, authors' names, keywords, and abstracts from the selected publications. Each field was analyzed to determine whether to retain or discard each publication based on its relevance to our research objectives. Publications were retained if they clearly demonstrated a connection to both salmon and stocking. For example, some publications focused exclusively on

Atlantic salmon farming or aquaculture, described field experiments involving the release of tagged salmon into rivers, or examined the effects of salmon stocking on other species. Although many of the 2,066 publications fell under the “Fisheries” category (Figure 2.1), it was challenging to exclude all publications categorized as “Fisheries” or “Aquaculture” since Atlantic salmon is primarily fished in rivers. Even purely ecological or evolutionary studies on Atlantic salmon may be classified under the “Fisheries” category in the Web of Science (WOS).

To ensure the accuracy of our selection, we conducted two consecutive screening rounds based on the title, keywords, and abstract. These resulted in the retention of 110 publications. Notably, one of these was a book chapter that was not explicitly identified as such by WOS and was therefore excluded from our final selection. Consequently, our final collection comprised 109 publications. Of these, two could not be downloaded, and 29 were already included in our subsequent comprehensive review.

Figure 2.1: Web of Science category of the 2066 publications.

// 2.1.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE SELECTION

When we compared the names of the most prominent journals in the selected corpus (Figure 2.2 for the 2066 articles and Figure 2.3 for the remaining 109 publications), we can readily observe that our selection has narrowed down the topics to more ecological journals. As previously explained and as it was expected, most represented journals are associated with “Fishery” like *Fisheries Management and Ecology* or *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*. But those journals, like the *Journal of Fish Biology* are notably known for their scope on fish ecology and biology. When examining the year of the remaining 109 publications over the past two decades, no discernible pattern emerges (Figure 2.4).

Number of bibliography records per journal

only the first 25 journals are accounted for - 771 (37%) publications not plotted

Journal name

Query performed on the Web of Science™ database on March 5th, 2025. © SCIMABIO Interface

Figure 2.2: Journal name according to the number of publications inside (N=2066).

Number of bibliography records per journal

only the first 25 journals are accounted for - 22 (20%) publications not plotted

Journal name

Query performed on the Web of Science™ database on March 5th, 2025. © SCIMABIO Interface

Figure 2.3: Journal name according to the number of publications inside (N=109).

Number of bibliography records on WOS per publication year

Topic = (Atlantic salmon OR Salmo salar) AND (supplementation OR stocking OR supportive breeding)

Publication year

Query performed on the Web of Science™ database on March 5th, 2025. © SCIMABIO Interface

Figure 2.4: Number of publications per year (N=109).

12.2. CONCORDANCING AND TEXT ANALYSIS

Using the software Orange, we generated a word cloud (Figure 2.5) from the titles and abstracts of the 109 selected publications. The 20 most recurrent words, listed in order from most to least frequent, were: salmon, atlantic, **stocking**, fish, wild, hatchery, populations, river, salmo, salar, smolts, population, reared, genetic, stocked, survival, release, natural, density, and fry.

Apart from terms directly associated with salmon (salmon, atlantic, fish, salmo, salar, smolts, fry), several of the most recurrent words are particularly noteworthy. First, the term “wild” is widely used in studies related to stocking, typically referring to fish born in the river. The use and definition of this term are discussed in Section 3.1 of Chapter 3 (page 38). This word also resonates with “natural”, the 18th most recurrent word, raising questions about what constitutes a natural or wild individual.

The word “genetic” is the 14th most recurrent word, while no terms related to abundance or demography appear among the top 20. The first word associated with population management (i.e., “management”) is the 21st most frequent, and “conservation” ranks 27th. Notably, the word “abundance”, which would logically be expected to be prominent in the context of stocking, is only the 70th most recurrent word—ranking after terms such as genetics, fisheries, growth, diversity, size, production, stocks, mortality, and introgression. This suggests that the demographic effects of stocking operations have not been among the most frequently addressed topics in the literature.

Number of bibliography records on WOS per publication year

Topic = (Atlantic salmon OR Salmo salar) AND
(supplementation OR stocking OR supportive breeding)

Figure 2.5: Word cloud of the corpus from Orange software (N=109).

The predominance of the terms genetics, diversity, and introgression in the corpus, compared to the word abundance, is further supported by the most frequent bigrams (pairs of associated words) identified in the corpus (Table 2.1). Notably, the bigrams “genetic diversity” and “genetic structure” are among the most common, suggesting that diversity is primarily investigated from a genetic perspective, with less emphasis on phenotypic or behavioral diversity. Additionally, it is evident that the word “wild” most frequently co-occurs with “population” and “fish”, highlighting its use to denote the origin of

fish in contrast to hatchery-reared individuals.

Table 2.1: *Collocation scores for bigrams related to Atlantic salmon.*

Collocation	Score
atlantic salmon	1512.28
salmo salar	863.71
salmon salmo	546.22
hatchery reared	220.60
year old	143.31
lake ontario	124.12
soft release	123.06
non native	112.99
penobscot river	101.14
results suggest	97.73
case study	95.37
genetic diversity	88.58
genetic structure	79.16
salmon populations	72.57
reared atlantic	69.22
release fish	50.69
stocked fish	36.94
wild populations	33.59
wild fish	29.01
salmon population	23.11
hatchery fish	22.49
salmon stocked	20.78
salmon smolts	20.55
wild atlantic	16.69

Finally, we investigated the most recurrent topics within the 109 abstracts using the R package STM (R Core Team 2025, Roberts et al. 2019). The first topic primarily encompassed general terms related to salmon (Figure 2.6), while the second topic was more focused on issues of genetic diversity. The third topic was mainly concerned with conservation and management.

Figure 2.6: *Most recurrent topics in the abstracts of the corpus (N=109).*

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PART II

Stocking program: definition,
justification, methods

CHAPTER **3**

Context, definition, justification

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13.1. DEFINITIONS OF STOCKING AND RELATED TERMS

// 3.1.1 WILD AND WILDERNESS

As noted in the systematic review, one term commonly associated with stocking programs is the concept of wild fish. In most studies and scientific monitoring focused on stocking, this adjective typically refers only to the birthplace of individuals — that is, fish born in the river. This definition is useful for denoting and tracking the origin of each individual. However, it does not take into account genetic heritage, i.e., the origin of the parents. For example, juveniles produced by two parents born in a hatchery but reproducing in a river are still classified as wild.

From a purely epidemiological perspective, the Merriam-Webster dictionary defines wild as either “living in a state of nature and not ordinarily tame or domesticated”, “not subject to restraint or regulation”, or “characteristic of, appropriate to, or expressive of wilderness, wildlife”. Under this definition, individuals born in a river but descended from hatchery-reared parents cannot be considered truly wild, since genetic effects of domestication in hatchery parents are partly heritable (see Section III, page 49 for more details, Naish et al. 2007, Rodriguez Barreto et al. 2019). At the population scale, over the last 50 years, most French populations have been directly stocked or have received indirectly stocked individuals dispersing from other rivers. Nevertheless, many stocking programs continue to use the terms wild and wilderness as justification or goals.

This raises the question of wilderness and what defines a wild population or a wild salmon. A recent paper addressing salmon conservation and stocking programs critically examines this issue (Harrison and Berseth 2024). The authors emphasize that traditional conservation aims to preserve or restore “wild” salmon populations and “natural” ecosystems. However, in the Anthropocene — where human impacts are pervasive and ecosystems are altered — historical baselines of “wildness” and “wilderness” are increasingly difficult to define or achieve. The paper questions the usefulness of static or idealized concepts of “natural” or “wild” in contemporary salmon management. The authors argue that “wild”

should not be viewed as a fixed or pure state but rather as a dynamic, context-dependent condition. The presence of hatchery-origin fish and ongoing human influences means many salmon populations exist along a continuum from wild to managed or supplemented. Recognizing this continuum is essential for setting realistic conservation goals. Instead of striving to recreate historical pristine conditions, management should work with current environments and incorporate diverse knowledge systems, including Indigenous perspectives that emphasize reciprocal relationships with salmon and place.

Overall, there is no clear and simple answer to the question “Does this population or this salmon qualify as wild?” (Harrison and Berseth 2024). Managers and stakeholders should avoid defining a salmon population as purely wild. However, the current state of populations in terms of diversity — genetic, epigenetic, phenotypic, and behavioral — should be maintained, preserved, and reinforced. For consistency with the literature, we use the term **wild** to designate all individuals born in rivers, in contrast to **hatchery** or **captive** individuals born in hatcheries.

// 3.1.2 DEFINITION

Stocking, broadly defined, refers to the deliberate release of fish — typically juveniles or eggs — into natural or semi-natural environments to influence population dynamics or ecosystem services. In the literature, several terms are used interchangeably or with nuanced distinctions, including “stocking”, “enhancement”, “supplementation”, and “supportive breeding” (Bacon et al. 2015, Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Molony et al. 2003, Trushenski et al. 2015). The terminology often reflects the objectives and context of the intervention (Figure 3.1):

- **Restoration Stocking (Reintroduction):** The release of individuals into areas where the species has been extirpated, with the goal of re-establishing self-sustaining populations (Boyer et al. 2001, Gayou and Roguet 1996, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).
- **Mitigation Stocking:** Implemented to compensate for anthropogenic impacts such as habitat loss, reduced water quality, or the construction of dams (Glover et al. 2018, Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). This form of stocking aims to maintain population levels despite ongoing environmental degradation.
- **Fisheries Enhancement:** Stocking intended to increase fish abundance for recreational or commercial fisheries, often without explicit conservation objectives (Arrignon 1973, Molony et al. 2003, Ritter 1997, Trushenski et al. 2015, Zink et al. 2023).
- **Conservation Stocking:** The release of individuals to support the persistence of threatened populations, maintain genetic diversity, or prevent extinction. This approach is sometimes referred to as “conservation-oriented stocking” (Bacon et al. 2015, Harrison and Berseth 2024, Naish et al. 2007).
- **Supplementation Programs:** These programs involve the release of hatchery-reared fish into existing wild populations to augment natural recruitment, often as a temporary measure (Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

- **Captive Breeding and Supportive Breeding:** Involves maintaining broodstock in captivity for several generations, with the aim of producing offspring for release (Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

It is important to note that the boundaries between these categories are not always clear-cut, and a single stocking program may serve multiple purposes or shift objectives over time (Lennox et al. 2021, Naish et al. 2007).

Figure 3.1: Scheme of the different definitions of stocking programs. ©C. Bouchard

13.2. LAUNCHING OF STOCKING PROGRAM: WHY?

// 3.2.1 MOTIVATION AND JUSTIFICATION OF STOCKING PROGRAMS

Around the different types / definitions of stocking, motivations are diverse and have evolved in response to ecological, social, and political contexts. Historically, stocking was often seen as a straightforward solution to declining fish populations or fishing opportunities (Molony et al. 2003, Waples et al. 2007). The main motivations include:

- **Restoration of Extirpated Populations:** Stocking is used to reintroduce salmon to rivers

where they have disappeared. The classic restoration scenario is a river where salmon have disappeared following major habitat alteration. The Dordogne–Garonne plan of the late 1970s exemplifies this model, combining barrier removal, research on carrying capacity and large-scale fry releases (Boyer et al. 2001, Gayou and Roguet 1996). In such cases managers prioritise local broodstock (in the new version of the program) and assess whether juvenile production, not marine survival, is the limiting factor (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

- **Mitigation of Anthropogenic Impacts:** Stocking compensates for habitat degradation, dam construction, and other human activities that limit natural recruitment (Glover et al. 2018, Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). Where habitat quality has been reduced by dams, gravel extraction or intensive land use, stocking can be authorised as a compensatory measure pending full restoration. Examples mostly include dam-related programmes such as some programs in Sweden and Finland (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013, Ritter 1997). Assessments must show that habitat works alone cannot yet support recovery and that releases will not exacerbate density-dependent mortality.
- **Fisheries Enhancement and Recreational Opportunities:** A major driver of stocking is to increase fishing opportunities and support recreational or commercial fisheries (Ritter 1997, Salminen et al. 2007, Zink et al. 2023) like it was intended in the Bresle river (Arrignon 1973). Enhancement or supplementation are the terms often used in these contexts (Bacon et al. 2015, Fraser 2008). Programs justified under this rubric usually include a cost–benefit analysis — yet such analyses are seldom updated once stocking begins (Molony et al. 2003).
- **Conservation of Threatened Populations:** Stocking is used as a tool to prevent extinction, maintain genetic diversity, and support small or declining populations (Bacon et al. 2015, Harrison and Berseth 2024, Perrier et al. 2014). Salmon are also stocked as an umbrella species to catalyse basin-wide habitat works. As said previously, some authors question whether such “conservation stocking” truly preserves naturalness (Harrison and Berseth 2024, Naish et al. 2007).
- **Research and Scientific Experimentation:** Stocking provides opportunities to study population dynamics, genetic differentiation, and the effectiveness of management interventions (Matte et al. 2024, Perrier et al. 2014).
- **Socio-Political and Psychological Factors:** Stocking is sometimes maintained due to tradition, stakeholder expectations, or the perception that it is an immediate and simple solution to complex problems (Lennox et al. 2021, Molony et al. 2003, Naish et al. 2007, Radinger et al. 2023). In some cases, stocking is used as a substitute for addressing root causes of population decline, which may be politically or economically challenging to resolve (Waples et al. 2007). Also, numerous hatcheries were established as a political response to societal demands for harvest and conservation, which can make it difficult to properly evaluate the effects of such stocking programs (Naish et al. 2007).

Throughout this review, we use stocking as an umbrella term but retain specific labels — enhancement, supplementation, supportive breeding, conservation stocking, and restoration — when needed to clarify context and management intent. The ongoing debates about the naturalness of stocking

(Harrison and Berseth 2024) and the diversity of objectives behind stocking programs make it necessary to link definitions explicitly to ecological or societal goals. Given the variety of stocking program types, it is clear that their ultimate objectives differ, which implies that the methods to achieve these objectives also differ, as do the tools and approaches used to monitor program effects. Therefore, defining each stocking program by its ultimate objective is essential.

// 3.2.2 LAUNCHING BIAS OF STOCKING PROGRAMS IN A CONSERVATION PERSPECTIVE

Conservation biology and fisheries management are often seen as opposing fields, yet they share similar agendas, as both seek the long-term viability of fish stocks, albeit for different reasons. Conservationists focus on maintaining biodiversity, while fisheries managers aim to maximize productivity (Brown and Day 2002).

As reflected by the various types and objectives of stocking programs — excluding those aimed solely at fisheries enhancement — there are many drivers behind stocking initiatives with a conservation perspective. As noted by Glover et al. (2018), the decision to launch a stocking program is often driven by long-term declines in natural fish populations due to anthropogenic pressures. However, since most causes of salmon population declines are human-induced (see Section 1.2.2), the actions to be taken are frequently too complex, economically costly, socially sensitive, or politically challenging to resolve. Consequently, stocking programs are sometimes used as substitutes or “quick fixes” (Trushenski et al. 2015, Waples et al. 2007).

Stocking programs defined for conservation purposes (i.e., reintroduction, conservation, mitigation; see Figure 3.1) should involve **temporary** releases of hatchery fish to rebuild populations more rapidly than would be achieved by natural recovery, and should be involved when population abundance is **substantially below carrying capacity** as a result of overfishing, environmental catastrophes, or similar factors (Arago and Vauclin 2001, Lorenzen et al. 2012).

Supplementation programs are usually defined as the continued release of hatchery fish into existing populations (Lorenzen et al. 2012). In some cases, such programs may be implemented with a conservation objective when the targeted population is very small and declining, with the aim of reducing extinction risk. In these situations, releases should be moderate so as not to further depress the wild population (Lorenzen et al. 2012, Waples et al. 2007).

While scientific knowledge generally enables us to understand the threats acting on a population and to identify potential solutions, the definition and implementation of these solutions are often hindered by socio-political and economic factors (Thorstad et al. 2021). Stocking programs implemented to mitigate the impacts of dam construction—such as those on the Dordogne-Garonne in France (Gayou and Roguet 1996), or in Finland and Sweden (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013)—illustrate this challenge well.

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CHAPTER **4**

Launching of stocking program: how?

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Depending on the objectives—when they are clearly defined—methods used for stocking programs are highly variable in terms of the life stages stocked, how individuals are produced, the origin of broodstock, and where and when in the river individuals are released. Methods are often poorly described and/or unavailable in the scientific literature, especially for older programs, even if they are still ongoing.

For instance, in France, some programs or trials have produced individuals in ponds (Dumas 1981) or in nursery creeks (Prouzet and Gaignon 1981). However, most Atlantic salmon stocking programs across the species' distribution involve hatcheries (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Typically, these programs use artificial reproduction of a broodstock that is entirely or partially renewed each year, with fertilized eggs and subsequent juveniles incubated in hatcheries. The methods used often depend on the available historical facilities and hatcheries, resulting in practical modalities that are rarely modified over the course of a program.

Artificial reproduction and the crossing of adults—that is, how the egg batch from a female is distributed among one or several males—vary greatly among programs, depending on the facilities, historical local practices, and the ability to capture adults each year. In some cases, kelts (i.e., adults that have already spawned) can be reconditioned for breeding (Dumas and Barr 1991). The developmental stages of stocked individuals range from eyed eggs to smolts (Lennox et al. 2021, Milot et al. 2013, Prignon et al. 1999, Prouzet and Gaignon 1981), and can even vary within a single program (Prignon et al. 1999).

Here is a brief overview of the different methods; however, they are discussed in greater detail in the following sections, particularly in relation to the effects of stocking and the recommendations made by various authors.

4.1. DEVELOPMENTAL STAGES

Stocking can occur at various developmental stages (Table 4.1), each with distinct ecological and management implications. Some restoration and supportive breeding programs release fertilized eggs or newly hatched alevins directly into river gravels, aiming to maximize natural selection at early life stages and promote natural imprinting (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Prignon et al. 1999). The release of fry (first-feeding juveniles) or parr (older juveniles) is also common. These stages are more robust than eggs or alevins and have higher survival rates post-release, but may already exhibit some hatchery-induced traits (Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Milot et al. 2013). Releases at the smolt stage (juveniles preparing for sea migration) are frequently used in supportive breeding or mitigation programs, particularly where rapid population increases are desired or where downstream obstacles exist (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013, Naish et al. 2007). In rare cases, mature adults are released, typically for reintroduction or to supplement spawning stocks directly (Fraser 2008).

Table 4.1: *Developmental stages released in stocking programs and corresponding references. Some stages can be combined in some publications or programs.*

Developmental Stage	References
Fertilized eggs (eyed eggs)	Glover et al. (2018), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Prignon et al. (1999)
Alevins (newly hatched, with yolk sac)	Dumas (1979), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Prouzet and Gagnon (1981)
Fry (first-feeding juveniles)	Arrignon (1973), Dumas (1979), Fraser (2008), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Prouzet and Gagnon (1981), Saltveit (2006), Solås et al. (2019), Stringwell et al. (2014)
Parr (older juveniles)	Dumas (1979), Fraser (2008), García-Vega et al. (2025), Jokikokko et al. (2006), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Prignon et al. (1999), Skilbrei et al. (2010)
Pre-smolts	Prignon et al. (1999), Skilbrei et al. (2010), Zydlewski et al. (2014)
Smolts (preparing for sea migration)	Dumas et al. (1979), García-Vega et al. (2025), Gayou and Roguet (1996), Glover and Stephen (2023), Gorsky et al. (2009), Hyvärinen and Rodewald (2013), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Kallio-Nyberg et al. (2013), Milot et al. (2013), Naish et al. (2007), Roberts et al. (2009), Salminen et al. (2007), Stevens et al. (2019), Thorstad et al. (2012),
Mixed stages / Not clearly specified	Bousquet (1996), Dumas and Marty (1987), Gayou and Roguet (1996), Molony et al. (2003)

1.4.2. RELEASE SITE IN THE RIVER SYSTEM

The location of release is a key variable in stocking strategies (Table 4.2). Eggs or alevins are often released in upstream spawning habitats to encourage natural imprinting and dispersal, but also because, by definition, these habitats are favorable (Gayou and Roguet 1996, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009). Fry and parr may be released in nursery habitats with suitable shelter and food availability (Fraser 2008), although this practice can locally increase density-dependent competition with wild fry and parr. In some cases, artificial reproduction is carried out or eggs are incubated in nursery creeks connected to the river targeted by the stocking program, allowing the stocked fish to disperse naturally into the river (Prouzet and Gaignon 1981). Smolts are often released further downstream, sometimes below migration barriers or dams, to maximize survival and access to the sea (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013, Naish et al. 2007). In certain enhancement programs, fish are stocked directly into lakes or reservoirs to support recreational fisheries (Molony et al. 2003).

Table 4.2: *Release sites in the river system for stocking programs and corresponding references.*

Release Site	References
Upstream spawning grounds (headwaters, natural gravels)	Gayou and Roguet (1996), Gorsky et al. (2009), Johnsson et al. (2014), Jonsson and Jonsson (2009), Prouzet and Gaignon (1981), Vibert (1945)
Nursery habitats (side channels, nursery creeks, tributaries)	Arrignon (1973), Bousquet (1996), Dumas and Marty (1987), Fraser (2008), Gorsky et al. (2009), Mokdad et al. (2022), Prignon et al. (1999), Prouzet and Gaignon (1981), Wallace and Curry (2017)
Downstream/mainstem (including below migration barriers or dams)	Gayou and Roguet (1996), Gorsky et al. (2009), Kallio-Nyberg et al. (2013), Naish et al. (2007)
Lakes or reservoirs	Arrignon (1973), Molony et al. (2003)

1.4.3. HATCHERY TYPES AND REARING PRACTICES

The type of hatchery and rearing approach can influence the genetic and phenotypic characteristics of stocked fish (as reviewed in the next section). Most programs use standard flow-through or recirculating aquaculture systems, with artificial feeding and high-density rearing (Glover et al. 2018, Naish et al. 2007). Some facilities adopt practices to minimize domestication, such as using local wild broodstock, reducing rearing densities, and simulating natural conditions (Bacon et al. 2015, Perrier et al. 2014). Supportive breeding facilities focus on supplementing wild populations while minimizing the time offspring spend in captivity, often releasing them at early life stages (Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

1.4.4. BROODSTOCK ORIGIN AND GENETIC CONSIDERATIONS

Using local wild adults as broodstock is now commonly preferred in order to maintain local adaptations (Table 4.3) and genetic diversity (Bacon et al. 2015, Perrier et al. 2014). In contrast, some programs rely on multi-generation captive lines, which can increase domestication and reduce fitness in the wild (Fraser 2008, Naish et al. 2007).

Table 4.3: *Broodstock origin in stocking programs and corresponding references.*

Broodstock Origin	References
Local wild-caught adults	Dumas and Marty (1987), Feuerstein et al. (2024), Gabián et al. (2022), García-Vega et al. (2025), Perrier et al. (2014), Prignon et al. (1999), Prouzet and Gaignon (1981), Vibert (1945), Witzemberger and Hochkirch (2011)
Mixed / Local and Non-local (e.g. foreign strains)	Almodóvar et al. (2020), Bousquet (1996), Dumas and Marty (1987), Dumas et al. (1979), García-Vega et al. (2025), Gayou and Roguet (1996), Horreo et al. (2008)
Non-local / Foreign strains	Bousquet (1996), Dumas et al. (1979), Gabián et al. (2022), Glover and Stephen (2023), Gorsky et al. (2009), Prouzet and Gaignon (1981)
Multi-generation captive broodstock	Fraser (2008), García-Vega et al. (2025), Milot et al. (2013), Naish et al. (2007)
Reconditioned kelts (post-spawning adults)	Dumas and Barr (1991)

4.5. TEMPORAL PATTERNS AND DURATION

One-time releases are used for restoration or reintroduction, with the goal of establishing self-sustaining populations (Gayou and Roguet 1996). In contrast, regular releases over multiple years are common in mitigation, supplementation, or enhancement programs (Fraser 2008, Molony et al. 2003). Conservation-oriented releases are ideally temporary and should be phased out as wild populations recover (Lorenzen et al. 2012).

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PART III

Evaluation and stocking effects

CHAPTER

5

Comparative biology

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5.1. A MAJOR CAUSES OF DIFFERENCES: DOMESTICATION

Domestication is a central concern in fish supplementation and stocking programs, as human intervention can drive evolutionary change over surprisingly short time scales (Fraser 2013, Hutchings 2014). Both introductions and stocking have provided strong evidence for local adaptation and rapid evolutionary responses in salmonids, often driven by the artificial conditions of hatcheries (Glover et al. 2018, Hutchings 2014). Cultured fish enter a process of domestication, which encompasses both developmental and genetic changes in response to the culture environment (Lorenzen et al. 2012, Naish et al. 2007). In practice, most hatchery programs produce primarily “captive-type” individuals, as management strategies aimed at maintaining or re-establishing “wild-like” characteristics tend to be complex and costly (Fraser 2008, Lorenzen et al. 2012).

Developmental responses — i.e., the range of phenotypes expressed by a given genotype — are particularly pronounced in fish due to their high phenotypic plasticity compared to higher vertebrates (Lorenzen et al. 2012). The most basic form of domestication arises from inadvertent responses to the culture environment, which can quickly lead to the evolution of captive-adapted types (Lorenzen et al. 2012). While the culture environment often reduces selection pressures on traits important for survival in the wild, it introduces new pressures favoring traits that are beneficial in captivity (Glover et al. 2018, Lorenzen et al. 2012). Genetic adaptation to captivity frequently involves alleles that are rare or even deleterious in the wild but become advantageous, or at least neutral, under hatchery conditions (Lorenzen et al. 2012).

Moreover, selection for specific traits in captivity can cause correlated changes in other traits, sometimes with unintended consequences, due to genetic linkage, pleiotropy, or resource-based selection of genotypes (Lorenzen et al. 2012, Perrier et al. 2014). A common response to the hatchery environment is accelerated development — cultured fish typically grow faster and mature earlier than

their wild counterparts (Lorenzen et al. 2012). This suite of changes, often termed the “domestication syndrome”, reflects a shift in life-history strategies: resources are reallocated toward rapid growth and reproduction at the expense of functions such as resource conservation, foraging, and predator avoidance, which are critical for fitness in complex and unpredictable natural environments (Lorenzen et al. 2012, Naish et al. 2007). As a result, hatchery-rearing not only affects ontogeny and growth rates but also alters a wide range of phenotypic and behavioral traits (Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007), potentially reducing the fitness of stocked fish in the wild (Fraser 2008, Glover et al. 2018, Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007).

I 5.2. DIFFERENCES WILD VS HATCHERY-REARED FISH

// 5.2.1 BEHAVIOR

Differences in behavioral traits between wild and hatchery-reared fish have been documented across multiple stocked species (Johnsson et al. 2014, Näslund 2021), a long-recognized issue in fisheries management (Johnsson et al. 2014). These disparities likely arise because hatchery environments, which are highly stable and ecologically simplified compared to natural habitats, promote adaptation to artificial conditions and the reinforcement of maladaptive behaviors (Johnsson et al. 2014, Näslund 2021). For example, the lack of environmental complexity in hatchery tanks reduces opportunities for behavioral stimulation, leading to deficits in traits critical for survival in the wild (Näslund 2021). According to Näslund (2021), the absence of predator exposure in hatcheries is a key driver of maladaptive behaviors, as reared fish never develop antipredator responses. The authors also highlight that hatchery-reared fish exhibit reduced learning and memory capacities relative to wild conspecifics. In this context, we review the most common behavioral differences observed between hatchery-reared and wild Atlantic salmon.

Downstream migration

Salmon, like other migratory fish species, must exhibit specific behaviors such as migration. Several studies have investigated differences between wild and hatchery-reared individuals in their downstream migration (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006), but the results are variable. For example, Vollset et al. (2017) found that hatchery-reared smolts migrate immediately after release, unlike their wild counterparts, suggesting that hatchery-reared individuals are bolder. In this context, the time required for an individual to resume normal activity after being introduced into a new environment is considered a proxy for boldness; individuals that quickly resume swimming activity are viewed as bolder (Brown et al. 2005, Conrad et al. 2011, Fraser et al. 2001), which is consistent with the behavior of fish raised in the stable environment of a hatchery tank. In addition, Birnie-Gauvin et al. (2018) found that stocking methods — particularly the developmental stage at which fish are released (i.e., fry, half-year-olds, or young-of-the-year) — influence both smolt size and the probability of migration. Specifically, they observed that fish stocked in the fall as half-year-olds (upper modal group) exhibited the highest emigration rates and emigrated later than other stocked fish.

Regarding migration phenology — the timing of migratory behavior — Kennedy et al. (2012)

found that hatchery-reared smolts migrated earlier than wild individuals. However, Larocque et al. (2020) reported that hatchery-reared and wild smolts migrated at the same time, while Saltveit (2006) found hatchery smolt migrated later than wild smolts. These results suggest that hatchery-reared smolts may sometimes differ in the timing of their downstream migration, often migrating earlier, but this seems to depend on environmental conditions and stocking practices in hatchery production and release.

Migration speed is also important, as it influences the time spent in the river, the likelihood of predation, and the energy required for migration. Vollset et al. (2017) found that hatchery-reared smolts survived better than wild fish because they spent less time in the river. In contrast, Larocque et al. (2020) and Urke et al. (2013) found similar migration speeds between the two origins. As with phenology, migration speed may vary depending on environmental conditions. However, if individuals migrate faster and arrive earlier at sea, they may experience a mismatch with available trophic resources (Durant et al. 2007, Satterthwaite et al. 2014, Wilson et al. 2023). Finally, Urke et al. (2013) found that hatchery-reared smolts may use the same migration routes as wild smolts.

Overall, some differences in downstream migratory behavior may exist between hatchery-reared smolts and their wild counterparts, but these differences are not consistent across all systems. Therefore, it is necessary to monitor migratory behavior in each system to assess potential differences and their effects on survival. Furthermore, wild kelts — individuals that spawn in the river and return to the sea — had higher estuarine survival than hatchery-spawned kelts, which are individuals that spawn in a hatchery and are then released into the river (Bordeleau et al. 2018).

Straying and upstream migration

The counterpart to downstream migration is upstream migration, which is crucial because it determines the availability of reproductive adults in rivers. Individuals may either return to their natal river or disperse to another river. In Atlantic salmon, the homing rate is typically around 80–90%, meaning that 10–20% of individuals stray to rivers other than their natal one (Keefer and Caudill 2014). In this context, hatchery-reared individuals have been shown to display higher straying rates than wild fish (Horreo et al. 2012, Jonsson et al. 2003, Perrier et al. 2013b). This is also associated with lower upstream migration performance (Ritter 1997) and a greater tendency for reverse movement behaviors, such as downstream migration during the upstream migration phase. Hatchery-reared fish also exhibit a higher number of river entries and thus cover greater distances during migration (Nilsen et al. 2023). Altogether, these findings indicate that hatchery-reared individuals tend to have more maladaptive homing behaviors compared to wild fish.

Mate choice, reproductive behavior, reproductive success

Following upstream migration, individuals must reproduce. Reproduction is crucial because, from both managers' and anglers' perspectives, it is the source of new cohorts in the population. While knowing the number of potential spawners (i.e., adult returns) is useful, understanding their actual reproductive output is probably even more important. Even with a low number of adults, a popu-

lation may be maintained if they produce enough juveniles — at least for a short period (i.e., a few generations) and in the absence of catastrophic environmental or demographic events. However, the number of adults that successfully produce juveniles drives the genetic diversity of the population; the more breeders contribute offspring, the higher the genetic diversity. This number of effective breeders is not necessarily related to the total number of returning adults (i.e., available spawners), as sexual competition, spatial distribution of breeders, and the participation of mature parr can all influence the number of effective breeders (Bacles et al. 2018). Additionally, the more a female mates with different males, the greater the genetic diversity of her offspring, which in turn increases her fitness (i.e., the survival of her juveniles will be higher; Garant et al. (2005)). First, hatchery-reared individuals may have lower reproductive success than wild counterparts, partly because they typically have higher straying rates. Straying individuals (dispersers) generally have lower reproductive success than those spawning in their natal river, primarily due to local adaptation (Mobley et al. 2019). Second, regarding spawning site selection, Hagelin et al. (2016) found that hatchery-reared individuals move more erratically compared to wild fish. Hatchery-reared fish also hold their position for shorter periods during spawning, which likely results in a shorter spawning duration. Third, in a study monitoring the reproduction of stocked Atlantic salmon in Lake Ontario, Scott et al. (2005) observed interspecific mate guarding and courtship between stocked Atlantic salmon and other stocked salmonids (Chinook salmon and brown trout). These results provide evidence that stocked individuals may exhibit maladaptive mating behaviors, and that other stocked species (including trout) may interfere with the reproduction of Atlantic salmon. Fourth, at the spawning sites, hatchery-reared individuals are less competitive than wild fish and produce less juveniles (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006). For instance, in an experiment *in natura*, the breeding success of hatchery-reared salmon was less than one-third of the breeding success of wild fish (Fleming et al. 2000). Also, hatchery-reared females of another salmonid (*Oncorhynchus kisutch*) are less competitive to acquire a nesting territory than wild females (Fleming and Gross 1993).

Habitat choice and feeding behavior

Several studies have examined differences in feeding behavior between wild and hatchery-reared Atlantic salmon (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009). In a study, wild juveniles were compared to hatchery-reared juveniles (stocked as alevins), revealing that stocked individuals consumed a greater number of prey items, though the wet mass of their stomach contents did not differ significantly from wild fish (Hatanpää et al. 2020). This lack of divergence in stomach wet mass suggests potential differences in prey selection, with stocked fish possibly targeting smaller or less energetically valuable prey types compared to their wild counterparts. In addition, a long-term population monitoring study hypothesized that the failure of fry stocking to translate into increased parr production in the river could be due to the inability of stocked fry to appropriately select overwintering habitats from their stocking locations (Glover and Stephen 2023).

Social behavior, boldness & antipredator behavior

Several studies have investigated differences in social behavior between wild and hatchery-reared individuals (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006; 2009). Hatchery-reared salmon are generally more aggressive (Blanchet et al. 2008, Fenderson et al. 1968), exhibit more intense social interactions (Fenderson et al. 1968), and tend to be more dominant than wild fish (Fenderson et al. 1968). However, the outcome

of competition between wild and hatchery-reared juveniles can vary depending on environmental conditions, particularly if wild fish have prior access to feeding habitats (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006). The higher aggressiveness of hatchery-reared salmon may partly explain their lower survival in natural environments, as it can lead to reduced feeding time, excessive energy expenditure, and increased exposure to predators (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006). Additionally, hatchery-reared individuals are more likely to migrate during daylight, in contrast to wild fish, which may increase their predation risk and further decrease survival (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006). However, schooling behavior among hatchery-reared individuals may mitigate this negative effect by diluting the risk of predation (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006).

Altogether, hatchery-reared fish exhibit a wide range of behavioral differences compared to their wild counterparts (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006; 2009, Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007). While some of these differences may be mitigated depending on environmental conditions (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006), the overall outcome is typically reduced fitness — that is, lower survival and juvenile production — among hatchery-reared fish (Fleming et al. 2000, Jonsson and Jonsson 2006, Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007).

// 5.2.2 PHENOTYPIC DIFFERENCES

Phenotypic differences between wild and hatchery-reared salmon have been widely studied, with various distinctions observed in body form and size (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006; 2009). These differences arise from the plasticity of salmon during their early life stages (Bailey et al. 2010, Stringwell et al. 2014). For example, wild salmon parr in the Aulne River were found to be shorter than stocked parr (Laffaille 2011). This difference was observed three months after stocking, indicating that it is temporally stable over several months of juvenile life (Laffaille 2011), and it persists until the smolt stage, with hatchery-reared smolts being longer and larger than their wild counterparts (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). Typically, hatchery-reared smolts are longer and heavier than wild smolts (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006), which is expected since they have access to abundant food in hatcheries and expend less energy on behaviors such as predator avoidance and competition for habitat or food. However, Kennedy et al. (2012) found contrasting, though not significant, results with hatchery-reared smolts being lighter and shorter; the differences were not statistically significant.

For a given length, other morphological differences are also observed between hatchery-reared and wild salmon. For instance, wild fish tend to have deeper heads and longer pectoral fins (Blanchet et al. 2008). Interestingly, Hatanpää et al. (2020) found that semi-wild fish (stocked as alevins) had a more slender body shape and longer fins than hatchery-reared fish stocked as parr, suggesting that stocking at earlier developmental stages may favor a more “natural” body shape through plasticity. This is also supported by the findings of Stringwell et al. (2014), who reported that fish stocked as fry had longer heads, thicker caudal peduncles, and a more streamlined body shape than fish kept 22 or 55 days longer in the hatchery. All these morphological patterns are better adapted to fast-flowing water and result from plasticity during early life stages. In another study, hatchery conditions were found to reduce the eye size of Burrishoole ranched grilse through plasticity (Long et al. 2023). Furthermore, a recent study also demonstrated that individuals from natural environments exhibited greater symmetry than those reared under semi-natural conditions (Hatanpää et al. 2025). Additionally, individuals from

natural environments had thinner pectoral fins (Hatanpää et al. 2025), a trait better suited to movement in fast-flowing water.

Altogether, these results clearly indicate that hatchery-reared salmon may exhibit phenotypic differences compared to wild fish, due to both phenotypic plasticity and domestication (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006; 2009). Another important eco-evolutionary process that can generate phenotypic differences as a result of stocking is outbreeding depression. Stocked individuals may reproduce *in natura* with both other stocked fish and wild individuals (Le Cam et al. 2015). For example, the Sélune River was stocked from 1989 to 1997 with juveniles originating from the Aulne and Gave d'Oloron rivers. When examining the phenotype and genotype of individuals, authors found that hybrids resulting from wild x stocked matings were smaller and lighter than the mean values for the parental populations, a result indicative of outbreeding depression (Le Cam et al. 2015). In such cases, this means there is a reduction in fitness (selective value) observed in offspring produced by cross-breeding between individuals from genetically distant populations or from populations adapted to distinct environments.

// 5.2.3 DIFFERENCES IN LIFE HISTORY TRAITS

We have seen that hatchery rearing alters the relationship between phenotypes and genotypes through phenotypic plasticity. Another process closely linked to plasticity is ontogeny, which is strongly affected by hatchery practices. When examining ontogenetic differences between wild and hatchery-reared fry, Bailey et al. (2010) found that hatchery conditions advanced fry development by more than 30 days, potentially impacting phenology. According to the match-mismatch and ready-or-not hypotheses, hatchery-reared fry may experience strong natural selection due to developmental asynchrony (Bailey et al. 2010). These ontogenetic differences can subsequently lead to numerous differences in life history traits.

Most studies have found that hatchery-reared salmon exhibit faster growth rates (Birnie-Gauvin et al. 2018, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Long et al. 2023), resulting in differences in migration phenology and the timing of smoltification. For example, Saltveit (2006) reported that stocked fish smoltify earlier (at 1 or 2 years old) than wild fish (at 3 or 4 years old), and thus smoltify at a smaller size. An extensive common-garden experiment conducted over three cohorts of domesticated, hybrid, and wild Atlantic salmon families, in which eyed eggs were planted in riverbeds in late winter, found that smolt age was influenced by origin, with domesticated and wild smolts displaying mean ages of 1,429 and 1,532 days from fertilization to smoltification, respectively (Skaala et al. 2019). Interestingly, growth rates during the post-smolt and marine phases are faster for wild fish than for hatchery-reared salmon (Jonsson et al. 1996, Long et al. 2023).

The age at first reproduction may also be influenced by hatchery practices, leading to differences between stocked and wild salmon. While Saltveit (2006) found a higher proportion of MSW¹ individuals among stocked salmon, and García-Vega et al. (2025) reported that only stocked individuals reached 3SW in the Bidasoa River (Spain), most studies have found a lower proportion of MSW salmon among stocked Atlantic salmon compared to wild fish (Jonsson and Jonsson 2006; 2009, Kallio-Nyberg et al.

¹Multiple Sea Winter, see Glossary I.i, page 24

2013, Ritter 1997). MSW individuals are important for salmon populations, as MSW are female-biased and those females have higher fecundity and produce larger eggs than 1SW females (Fleming 1996, Jonsson et al. 1996). In another study, authors found that fecundity was similar between hatchery-reared and wild females, but eggs from wild females were 1.12 times heavier than those from hatchery females.

In Atlantic salmon, some individuals may mature in the river before downstream migration, i.e., as precocious or mature parr (Fleming 1996; 1998). This phenomenon is especially important in populations at the southern edge of the distribution, where participation of mature male parr in reproduction increases genetic diversity and female fitness by raising paternity share (Bagliniere and Maisse 1985, Garant et al. 2002, Garcia-Vazquez et al. 2001, Grimardias et al. 2010, Juanes et al. 2007, Martinez et al. 2000, Myers and Hutchings 1987, Saura et al. 2008). Although early maturation is partly heritable (Åsheim et al. 2023, Gjerde 1984, Sinclair-Waters et al. 2022), males used as broodstock are unlikely to be early maturing individuals, which may reduce the transmission of this life history trait (Hutchings 2014). Finally, regarding reproduction, some salmon may return to sea after spawning (these are called kelts) and reproduce in subsequent seasons. However, a study of kelts from the Penobscot River found that those used in hatcheries had low survival rates (23.6% against more than 65% in the river Imsa or more than 40% in the Burrishoole river), potentially leading to a decline in iteroparity in the river (Maynard et al. 2018).

// 5.2.4 GENETIC AND EPIGENETIC DIFFERENCES

Here, we discuss only the differences between wild salmon and stocked individuals whose parents originate from the target population, not from parents caught in other populations. Undoubtedly, if parents do not come from the stocked population, numerous genetic and epigenetic differences between stocked and wild individuals may arise due to local adaptation—even in spatially proximate populations, as observed in France (Perrier et al. 2013b). Genetic differences between wild and hatchery-reared Atlantic salmon may first result from domestication selection, meaning that natural selection is relaxed in hatcheries compared to rivers and that other selective pressures may emerge (Fraser 2008, Naish et al. 2007).

Another source of genetic differences, particularly in genetic diversity, is that the selection of adults for broodstock usually captures only a small portion of the genetic diversity present in the population. For instance, the reduced genetic diversity observed in stocked juveniles compared to the wild population is partly due to the limited number of females used, the overrepresentation of some MSW individuals (Horreo et al. 2008), or broodstock selection practices (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009). Since conservation stocking programs mainly target populations with low numbers, stakeholders are often constrained in the number of adults available for broodstock. Some studies have investigated these genetic differences, but the genetic effects of stocking programs are mainly addressed at the population scale *in natura* (see the corresponding section 6.1.1, page 64).

Domestication in hatcheries may also alter DNA methylation, resulting in differences in methylated regions between the sperm of wild and captive-reared males (Rodriguez Barreto et al. 2019). These differences affect genes associated with transcription, neural development, olfaction, and ag-

gression. More importantly, they are also found in the offspring, suggesting that epigenetic modifications may contribute to phenotypic and genetic differences between wild and hatchery-reared fish (Rodriguez Barreto et al. 2019).

// 5.2.5 DIFFERENCES IN HEALTH AND MICROBIOME

Depending on broodstock origin, crossing practices, hatchery environment, and sanitary conditions, stocked individuals may differ from their wild counterparts in health status and microbiome composition. While this question has not received extensive attention, farmed salmon provide useful insights. It is well established that farmed Atlantic salmon are more susceptible to parasites such as sea lice (Glover and Skaala 2006). Specifically, farmed salmon exhibit significantly higher infection levels than hybrid and wild counterparts, indicating differences in susceptibility to sea lice infection (Glover and Skaala 2006).

For Atlantic salmon stocked from hatcheries, a variety of pathologies are more frequent compared to wild salmon, including spinal deformities, cataracts, fin erosion, and liver damage (Lorenzen et al. 2012). As in other forms of livestock production, the high density and confinement of individuals in hatcheries promote parasite infections (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Otolith deformations, such as vaterite formation, are also more common in hatchery-reared individuals (Delaval et al. 2021).

Some studies have investigated differences in the microbiome between hatchery-reared and wild salmon. For example, hatchery conditions and practices influence the host gut microbiome (Andres et al. 2025, Katchkin-Stewart et al. 2024). These effects can persist after stocking (e.g., after transfer to sea; Katchkin-Stewart et al. 2024). Specifically, lactic acid bacteria from the Lactobacillaceae family replace commensals from Enterobacteriaceae and Clostridiaceae in hatchery-reared parr compared to wild parr (Lavoie et al. 2018). This means that hatchery-reared parr host a more generalist bacterial community, whereas the microbiota of wild parr is much more specialized. In addition to these community differences, the hatchery environment may reduce gut microbial diversity, especially when fish are vaccinated, as is commonly done in hatcheries (e.g., vaccination against bacterial kidney disease, BKD; Andres et al. 2025).

// 5.2.6 FITNESS DIFFERENCES

Negative effects of hatchery are found in several salmonids due to three potential mechanisms: deleterious mutations accumulation, inbreeding depression, and domestication selection (Araki et al. 2008). The latter is the most likely since mutation rate is known to be low for salmon and negative effects are found already for the first generation. Fitness measures consistently reveal lower survival and reproductive success (RS) of hatchery-reared fish stocked in the wild compared to their wild counterparts (Araki et al. 2009, Milot et al. 2013, Perrier et al. 2013a).

Reproductive success - RS

Concerning the reproductive component of fitness, namely reproductive success, several studies have found that hatchery-reared salmon exhibit lower reproductive fitness compared to wild salmon (Araki et al. 2009, Bouchard et al. 2022b, Dayan et al. 2024, Jonsson et al. 2019, Milot et al. 2013, O'Sullivan et al. 2020, Perrier et al. 2013b). For instance, Milot et al. (2013) reported that the relative reproductive success of hatchery-reared salmon is nearly half that of wild salmon (0.55). A study on other salmonids (steelhead and coho salmon) found that the reproductive success of hatchery-reared fish released into the wild decreased after only a single generation of integrated hatchery rearing (Thériault et al. 2011). Conversely, Dayan et al. (2024) demonstrated that just one generation in the wild is sufficient to restore diminished reproductive success: wild-born descendants of two hatchery-reared salmon stocked in the river produced significantly more offspring than hatchery-origin fish and a similar number to wild fish.

Some explanations for these differences arise from behavioral differences associated with mating. Additionally, gamete quality can be lower in hatchery-reared salmon compared to wild salmon (Biernaczyk et al. 2012). Interestingly, this is particularly true for males, whose gamete quality is more dependent on environmental conditions, whereas in females it is mostly determined by individual characteristics. Finally, Bouchard et al. (2022b) found that captive-bred salmon stocked as parr had fewer mates than wild salmon. Overall, the differences in reproductive success (RS) highlight the importance of not relying solely on counts of returning adults when evaluating a stocking program, especially if its aim is population conservation. Indeed, a returning adult that is hatchery-reared and stocked does not have the same productivity as a wild adult.

Survival

Globally, several studies have found lower survival rates for hatchery-reared salmon compared to wild fish (Bailey et al. 2010, Larocque et al. 2020, Perrier et al. 2013a;b). Specifically, Perrier et al. (2013a) found that stocked salmon had survival rates 10 to 25 times lower than wild fish, with differences observed at all life stages. Stocked fry experienced a 24–81% reduction in overall survival compared to wild fry (Bailey et al. 2010). Even introgressed parr had lower survival than wild parr (Wacker et al. 2021). Lower survival rates have also been reported for stocked smolts, with naturally reared smolts being 13.9 times more likely to survive than hatchery-reared smolts (Larocque et al. 2020). This indicates that significant differences in survival can occur even over short timescales (such as during downstream migration) and at life stages not considered highly sensitive (e.g., not just fry).

From an integrative perspective, the river production of smolts per female decreased as the proportion of wild females declined, indicating a real difference in the survival or production of smolts by female type (wild vs. hatchery-reared; Jonsson et al. 2019). Hatchery-reared families showed 30–70% lower survival rates compared to wild families (Skaala et al. 2019), with survival rates ranging from 0.5 to 3.7% (average 1.8%) for hatchery-reared families, compared to 1.5% to 6.0% (average 3.8%) for wild families over three cohorts. The wild-to-domesticated survival ratios were 1:0.63, 1:0.35, and 1:0.43 across the three respective cohorts (Skaala et al. 2019). Overall, selection against hatchery-reared phenotypes could theoretically result in both demographic and genetic costs due to these differences in survival.

Carry-over and transgenerational effects

A carry-over effect refers to a situation where an individual's experiences, conditions, or environment during one stage of its life (or one season) have delayed effects that influence its phenotype, performance, or fitness at a later stage or in a subsequent season (O'Connor et al. 2014). We have seen that hatchery-reared individuals, even those originating from wild-caught parents, may exhibit differences in phenotype, behavior, survival, and reproductive success, highlighting the presence of carry-over effects. While it is difficult to explicitly detect carry-over effects *in natura* in relation to stocking, this phenomenon was directly tested by Araki et al. (2009) in another salmonid species (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). The authors used parentage analysis to estimate the reproductive fitness of wild-born descendants of captive-bred parents in a supplemented population. Relative to the reproductive fitness of trout from two wild parents, they found that the relative reproductive fitness was 37% in wild-born trout from two hatchery-reared parents and 87% in those from one hatchery-reared and one wild parent. These results provide strong evidence for a carry-over effect.

The negative effects of hatchery rearing are not limited to individual carry-over effects but can also be transgenerational. Notably, and of particular concern, the results of Araki et al. (2009) indicate a transgenerational carry-over effect supported by other studies (Christie et al. 2012, Dayan et al. 2024, O'Sullivan et al. 2020, Perrier et al. 2016, Thériault et al. 2011). For instance, several studies have found that deficits in reproductive success are not limited to the first generation, with reduced fitness observed in wild-born descendants of hatchery parents (Christie et al. 2012, Dayan et al. 2024, O'Sullivan et al. 2020, Thériault et al. 2011).

Together, these findings underscore that hatchery-origin fish are not ecologically equivalent to wild fish on over numerous aspect. For instance, population productivity at the mean value of the proportion of hatchery-reared fish across a 43-year monitoring period was reduced, on average, by 9.778% relative to hypothetical pure population (O'Sullivan et al. 2020). The cumulative effects across traits highlight the importance of integrating biological knowledge into stocking decisions, ensuring that management strategies account for the profound and multifaceted impacts of supplementation. The numerous differences also raises the question about what type of salmon are stocked *in natura*, especially for conservation stocking that aims to conserve the population (so its diversity in all aspects). All those differences represent a breeding ground with strong effects on the population *in natura*.

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CHAPTER **6**

Effects in natura

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6.1. EFFECTS ON SALMON POPULATIONS

While it is difficult *in natura* to have the necessary data to disentangle eco-evolutionary effects to management effects (e.g., when and where hatchery-reared fish are stocked), several studies found and highlighted for effects of released hatchery-reared fish on wild populations (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

// 6.1.1 GENETIC EFFECTS

Genetic effects are probably the most studied effects *in natura* with multiple populations studied and with question raised since a long-time (Ritter 1997). Due to the domestication process, stocking hatchery-reared salmon may result in the introgression (see Glossary III.i, page 66) of poorly adapted genes into a local population leading to outbreeding depression or maladaptation (Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007, Naish et al. 2007). Indeed, stocking favor domesticated genotypes through introgression (Hagen et al. 2019). *In natura*, stocking may lead to introgressive hybridization (see Glossary III.i, page 66) between wild salmon and hatchery-reared conspecifics (Ozerov et al. 2016). Some genomic regions seem more prone or vulnerable to introgressive hybridization (Ozerov et al. 2016), leading potentially more intense the transmission and fixation of deleterious alleles.

Consequences of introgression are not found only during the stocking period but may endure in time with introgression of allochthonous genes found 10 years after the end of stocking (Horreo et al. 2014) or even 24-25 year in spanish rivers (Gabián and Morán 2019). Authors hypothesized that salmonids that experience previous introgression events would be more prone to mate with allochthonous individuals (Horreo et al. 2014). In addition, for some populations genetic introgression from stocked salmon are also concomittent with introgression with escaped farmed salmon (Karlsson et al. 2016). In overall, effects and consequences of genetic introgression due to stocking are found directly in the stocked population but also among populations. In a recent review, over 207 reviewed

papers, 126 articles studied potential effects among which 108 articles (84%) found adverse or minimally adverse effects indicating that when genetic effects are looked for, adverse or minimally adverse effects are commonly found (McMillan et al. 2023).

Local adaptation and genetic diversity within population

The first question on a genetic perspective is notably on the genetic diversity, whether to know stocked salmon raise, diminish, or do not impact genetic diversity of stocked population (e.g., number of alleles and allelic frequencies). Indeed, conservation stocking aims to maintain or enhance genetic diversity to ensure and preserve the potential for local population (see Glossary III.i, page 66) (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Fraser 2008), especially for small populations that are the more at risk (Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007). But domestication through stocking may shift allelic frequencies and fix deleterious alleles that cannot be purged after stocking (Fraser 2008, Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007). One of the most studied population on that topic is the river Sella for which a genetic deterioration has been found with three main changes: loss of native and distinctive alleles, introgression in the contemporary River Sella sample, reduction in the effective number of breeders (see Glossary III.i, page 66) and effective population size (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Fraser 2008). In opposition, some rare case of no genetic effect have been found like for the river Bidasoa in Spain; results cited by García-Vega et al. (2025) but the original work was not available for this review.

Additionally to the fixation of deleterious alleles or changes in allelic frequencies, stocking may diminish the number of effective breeders (N_e) depending on the proportion of stocked fish in the population (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Fraser 2008, Hagen et al. 2021, Naish et al. 2007). While the census size of the population (N_c , see Glossary III.i, page 66) may logically increase due to stocking if more adult return (i.e., addition of more individuals in the population), the variance in the reproductive success (RS) also increased (see previous chapter for explanations of the lowered RS of hatchery-reared fish, (Perrier et al. 2016)). Stocking thus induces Ryman-Laikre effect by increasing N_c and decreasing N_e (Hagen et al. 2021, Perrier et al. 2016, Ryman and Laikre 1991). Such effect is important since N_e necessarily represents a key element to keep a certain level of genetic diversity in the population.

Monitoring genetic effects within a population need to be done periodically. Indeed, across a monitoring, a Ryman-Laikre effect was observed for 11 cohorts over 19 (five populations and nine years), indicating potential variation in time and space in the occurrence of the Ryman-Laikre effect (Hagen et al. 2021). One explanation of the variations in the occurrence of the Ryman-Laikre effect is the proportion of hatchery-reared salmon in the population ranging from 0.08 to 0.83 (Hagen et al. 2021). Moreover, when non-native broodstock are used, stocking may initially increase the local genetic diversity but the introduction of a foreign genome into a wild native population could damage local adaptations (Garcia de Leaniz et al. 2007). Across a long monitoring, the genetic impact of historical stocking activities (40-50 years ago) on a contemporary population has been tested. In this population, hatchery-reared salmon from Scotland and Iceland have been stocked into the river Dart in England during 1960s. The long-term impact seemed variable among tributaries and the river, with a long-term effect appearing minimal in the river and more important in a tributary where a closer genetic relationship with the donor populations was found (Finnegan and Stevens 2008). Fraser (2008) reviewed several stocking programs notably under the genetic scope and highlight that most of them had the

same caveat: a loss of heterozygosity and allelic richness.

GLOSSARY III.i: Genetic diversity, eco-evolutionary terms, ...

census size The total number of individuals in a population.

number of effective breeders The total number of individuals in a population that effectively produced juveniles, which may reflect genetic diversity or evolutionary potential due to variance in reproductive success or connectivity.

local adaptation The evolution of traits in a population that enhance fitness in its native environment, often at the cost of reduced performance in foreign habitats.

introgression The transfer of genetic material from one species or population into another (here from hatchery-reared salmon to wild salmon) through hybridization and repeated backcrossing, which can alter adaptive potential or disrupt local adaptation.

hybridization Interbreeding between genetically distinct populations or species, potentially generating novel genetic combinations but risking maladaptive traits or outbreeding depression.

introgressive hybridization A process where genes from one population/species infiltrate another's gene pool via hybridization and backcrossing, often altering genetic architecture and fitness outcomes.

inbreeding Inbreeding is the mating or reproduction between individuals that are closely related genetically, resulting in increased homozygosity and a corresponding decrease in genetic diversity within a population

inbreeding depression is the reduction in biological fitness (such as lower survival, fertility, or overall health) that results from inbreeding, due to the increased expression of deleterious recessive alleles and loss of genetic diversity. Here, when descendants of hatchery-reared x hatchery-reared parents have a lower fitness than their parents.

outbreeding depression reduction in fitness that occurs when individuals from genetically distant populations or groups interbreed and due to genetic incompatibilities (e.g., disrupted coadapted gene complexes) or maladaptive intermediate phenotypes. Here, when descendants of hatchery-reared x wild parents have a lower fitness than their parents.

Local adaptation and genetic diversity among populations

Not only is genetic diversity within populations important, but also among populations, especially when these populations are connected by gene flow within a metapopulation, as in Brittany (France; Perrier et al. 2013a). Genetic diversity among salmon populations, even within a metapopulation, arises notably from local adaptation processes, since environments differ among rivers (Ayllon et al. 2006, Gabián et al. 2022). Local adaptation (its absence in fact) is a key reason for the failure of stocking programs when foreign salmon are used (Gabián et al. 2022). However, gene flow also occurs through the dispersal of individuals (Hendry et al. 2004, Jonsson et al. 2003, Perrier et al. 2013a, Salmenkova 2017). Dispersal is important as it may allow demographic, genetic, and evolutionary rescue by introducing new alleles into recipient populations (Carlson et al. 2014, see Figure 1 and Box 1). This underlines the importance of maintaining genetic diversity among populations through dispersal (Lamarins et al.

2022b). However, stocking can affect genetic diversity among populations in various ways.

Even if a population is not directly stocked, its genetic diversity can be influenced by stocked salmon, since hatchery-reared fish or hybrids tend to stray significantly more than wild fish (Jonsson et al. 2003), and homing ability is heritable (Hendry et al. 2004). Thus, stocked salmon may cause a breakdown of local adaptations and loss of fitness, but also increase and modify gene flow among populations, leading to genetic homogenization of populations, whether proximate or distant (Perrier et al. 2013a, Vasemägi et al. 2005).

In numerous stocking programs, foreign salmon are used as broodstock. As a result, in addition to the introgression of maladapted alleles, stocked populations become less differentiated from the population used for broodstock. In populations monitored in northeastern Spain and southwestern France, a high frequency of haplotypes characteristic of the foreign populations used as broodstock was observed, reflecting introgression (Campos et al. 2008, Vasemägi et al. 2005). In French populations (Gave d'Oloron, Aulne, Sélune) where foreign salmon have been stocked, admixture increased during the stocking period, leading to decreased genetic differentiation among stocked populations and the foreign population (Le Cam et al. 2015). Typically, introgression levels are correlated with the intensity of foreign stocking, as found in 14 European rivers (Campos et al. 2008). In rare cases, genetic diversity is not impacted by stocking, as observed among four Norwegian populations, two of which were stocked (Johnsen et al. 2014). Genetic diversity may also increase over a short timescale among stocked populations (Ciborowski et al. 2007). However, even if stocking is used occasionally and over a short timescale as a genetic or evolutionary rescue, increased or unchanged genetic diversity is not necessarily beneficial if the new alleles are deleterious or maladapted due to the use of foreign-origin salmon. A recent study has discussed the use of translocation, not stocking of hatchery-reared salmon, has a potential tool for genetic rescue (Pregler et al. 2023).

Furthermore, when foreign populations are used to stock several recipient populations, genetic diversity among these populations diminishes. For example, monitoring eight populations in France and Spain, Morán et al. (2005) found that F_{ST} values decreased after peak years of foreign stocking, with a reduction of 30% in five years. The decrease in genetic diversity between the stocked population and the foreign population is notably due to introgressive hybridization (i.e., admixture; Le Cam et al. 2015). For instance, the Ulla and Lérez rivers (Spain) showed significant genetic differences between historical samples from both rivers (Saura et al. 2006). Currently, populations inhabiting these two rivers are more genetically similar because stocked individuals originated from the same stock mixture (Saura et al. 2006). In other rivers in the southeast of the Atlantic salmon distribution range, the genetic differentiation observed between neighboring rivers before stocking appears to have been lost after only a decade of stocking with fish of foreign origin (Ayllon et al. 2006). The introgression of foreign-origin genes into local gene pools leads to a loss of genetic diversity in wild populations (Ayllon et al. 2006).

Zootechnical and monitoring perspectives

To monitor genetic diversity both within and among populations, and to assess how stocking impacts it, pre-stocking data are essential. However, such data are often unavailable, making it difficult to

accurately assess the genetic status of stocked populations. As a result, monitoring typically relies on comparing the genetic diversity of a given population to that of other populations (Nilsson et al. 2008).

Concerning genetic diversity, especially in conservation stocking programs, a key question is what aspect of Atlantic salmon we aim to preserve: is it simply the presence of Atlantic salmon in a river, or the unique genetic diversity and particularity of each population shaped by local adaptation (Harrison and Berseth 2024)? This question, and the two potential conservation objectives it implies, translate directly into the type of salmon we aim to produce in hatcheries for stocking. Should conservation hatcheries focus on producing a high-quality returning adult capable of reproduction and supporting human uses (e.g., fisheries), or should they prioritize producing a “genetically representative salmon” that reflects the wild population, does not detract from the total effective population size, and is capable of natural reproduction, with human-oriented priorities being secondary (Harrison and Berseth 2024)?

Apart from situations where foreign broodstock are used - which, by definition, makes it impossible to maintain the genetic diversity of the local population in the stocking pool - certain considerations can help preserve genetic diversity in hatchery-produced juveniles. With proper procedures, captive breeding programs may maintain or only slightly reduce genetic diversity losses. However, these procedures are challenging to implement, and some loss of fitness is inevitable (Fraser 2008, Lorenzen et al. 2012). Indeed, broodstock typically exhibit lower allelic richness than the source population (Blanchet et al. 2008), even when the broodstock is drawn from the “local population”, is diversified (e.g., 20 individuals with an equal sex ratio), and is partially renewed each year (50%; Blanchet et al. 2008).

To maximize genetic diversity in produced juveniles, the simplest and most effective measure is to increase the number of adults used as broodstock (Naish et al. 2007). However, because conservation stocking programs are often implemented in populations with negative growth rates, it is sometimes impossible to capture enough adults. Additionally, the crossing scheme used in the hatchery is another important factor in capturing the genetic diversity of the population in the juveniles produced (Machado-Schiaffino et al. 2007). The details of recommendations made by different studies are given in the corresponding section.

// 6.1.2 HABITAT CHOICE, DENSITY-DEPENDENCE AND DEMOGRAPHIC EFFECTS

We have already reviewed the numerous effects associated with hatchery rearing on individuals. However, stocked individuals also impact wild conspecifics *in natura* after release. For example, stocked parr can displace wild parr. In a study on the Aulne River (France), where 70,000–100,000 parr have been stocked annually since 1986, researchers compared habitat selection between wild and stocked parr under allopatric (only wild or hatchery parr present) and sympatric (both origins present) conditions (Laffaille 2011). Across 58 river sections sampled, wild and stocked parr occupied similar habitats in allopatric zones. However, in sympatric sections, wild parr shifted to glides to avoid riffles and pools dominated by stocked parr, suggesting displacement of wild individuals (Laffaille 2011). Similar habitat shifts in wild fish due to stocking have been observed in rainbow trout (Blanchet et al. 2007, Jonsson and Jonsson 2006), with concurrent reductions in wild trout survival (Blanchet et al. 2007).

By definition, stocking increases local population density. However, early life stages of salmon (pre-smolt) are regulated by density-dependent mortality. Releasing large numbers of juveniles may push local biomass beyond natural carrying capacity (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Since wild and stocked juveniles share the same carrying capacity, this can trigger compensatory responses and exacerbate density-dependent mortality in wild juveniles (Dauphin et al. 2017, Jonsson and Jonsson 2006). For example, parr densities at stocked sites in the Miramichi River (Canada) were lower than at unstocked sites (Wallace and Curry 2017), a pattern also observed in the Aulne River (France), where wild parr density correlated negatively with stocked parr density (Laffaille 2011). In their study, Bacon et al. (2015) found the ova density stocked in the river had a negative effect on the number of maximum emigrant rate while it was probably the best well-designed stocking program.

Negative demographic effects of stocking are evident at the population level. Over a 43-year period in the Burrishoole system, population productivity declined by an average of 9.8% relative to hypothetical pure wild populations when hatchery-origin adults were present (O'Sullivan et al. 2020). The study found that higher proportions of hatchery-reared adults reduced population viability (O'Sullivan et al. 2020). Similarly, the proportion of eggs from hatchery-origin parents negatively impacted wild egg-to-smolt survival (McGinnity et al. 2009). Despite the long-term use of stocking programs, few studies have modeled their demographic effects (Bowlby and Gibson 2011, Dauphin et al. 2017). A recent demographic model showed that continuous stocking initially boosted population size for 4–6 generations (demographic rescue), but subsequent fitness loss from domestication overwhelmed these benefits, leading to population declines (Bowlby and Gibson 2011). Thus, while short-term extinction risk may not increase immediately, long-term recovery via local adaptation may be compromised.

In some cases, stocking may benefit populations at critically low abundances by alleviating compensatory density dependence when populations are trapped at low abundance, thereby kick-starting population recovery (Lorenzen et al. 2012). However, empirical evidence for such benefits in small, declining populations remains limited (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Most studies, such as the one by Bowlby and Gibson (2011) and the one by Dauphin et al. (2017), used empirical data to fit their models, which were subsequently used to simulate different stocking scenarios. Any short-term demographic gains must be weighed against long-term risks, including transgenerational carry-over effects and threats to the long-term viability of wild populations (O'Sullivan et al. 2020). Indeed, while stocking may provide short-term demographic boosts, long-term impacts can include reduced reproductive success and lowered effective population sizes (Araki et al. 2009, Bouchard et al. 2022b, Dayan et al. 2024, Jonsson et al. 2019, Milot et al. 2013, O'Sullivan et al. 2020, Perrier et al. 2013b). Continuous supplementation can initially increase census numbers but may eventually depress population fitness due to carry-over effects, as shown in demographic models (Araki et al. 2009, Bowlby and Gibson 2011). Environmental changes, such as rising temperatures, may amplify these risks (McGinnity et al. 2009). For example, increases in winter water temperatures have been shown to negatively affect survival rates, and it has been argued that stocking is likely to exacerbate the impacts of climate change on natural populations (McGinnity et al. 2009).

Finally, stocking can have unintended socio-economic consequences. Without concurrent fisheries management, stocking may increase fishing pressure on populations (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013).

// 6.1.3 SANITARY

Some rare studies have investigated the sanitary impact *in natura* of salmon stocking. In fact, Ritter (1997) highlighted the sanitary issue as the potential first ecological negative effect. Sanitary impacts can be both on wild Atlantic salmon and other fish species, especially when parasites are transferred (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Such issue is not only found for salmon, but are also problematic for eel stocking (Kullmann et al. 2017). As shown in the previous chapter, hatchery-reared fish carry higher loads of pathogens and parasites, which can spill over into wild populations (Kullmann et al. 2017, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Ritter 1997). Also, altered gut microbiota (Lavoie et al. 2018) and physical deformities (Lorenzen et al. 2012) found at individual level may further compromise survival and resilience after release.

6.2. EFFECTS ON ECOSYSTEMS

Beyond direct impacts on salmon populations, stocking reshapes broader ecosystem dynamics across trophic, community, and abiotic dimensions. Understanding these cascading effects is crucial for assessing the full ecological cost of supplementation. While studies investigating the effects of salmon stocking on salmon populations *in natura* are rare, research on potential ecosystem-level effects is even scarcer.

At the community level, based on similar processes that drive negative effects on wild conspecifics, stocking Atlantic salmon may impact the abundance and life-history traits of other salmonid species, such as rainbow trout in Lake Ontario (Dietrich et al. 2008). Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) may also hybridize with brown trout (*Salmo trutta*), as the two species are closely related. Stocking Atlantic salmon may thus generate introgression between wild brown trout and stocked Atlantic salmon (Castillo et al. 2008).

Moreover, hatchery-reared salmon can affect communities and ecosystems, notably through alterations in local food webs (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Waknitz et al. 2003). Hatchery-origin fish frequently carry elevated pathogen loads, including sea lice, furunculosis, and bacterial kidney disease (Glover and Skaala 2006, Ritter 1997), which can spill over into wild populations, increasing disease prevalence. Recent microbiome studies reveal that hatchery fish harbor simplified and less resilient gut microbial communities (Lavoie et al. 2018), potentially increasing their susceptibility to pathogens and making them vectors of microbial disruption across ecosystems.

Additionally, altered migration, spawning, and carcass deposition patterns influence nutrient cycling, sediment transport, and primary production in river systems. For example, changes in the timing and location of spawning can modify bed disturbance regimes, while nutrient pulses from decomposing carcasses can shift algal and invertebrate community dynamics. Atlantic salmon is often considered an umbrella species because conservation programs targeting this species typically benefit rivers inhabited by numerous other species. This species also provides a variety of ecosystem services, including provisioning services (commercial and subsistence harvest), regulating services (food web dynamics, nutrient cycling, sediment turnover, serving as a host for freshwater pearl mussels, etc.), and numerous cultural services such as local identity, cultural heritage, tourism opportunities, and recreational

and psychological values (Watz et al. 2022). Therefore, any human actions that alter Atlantic salmon populations may have repercussions on all these ecosystem services.

6.3. SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFECTS

Stocking programs have historically been promoted for their potential socio-economic benefits, particularly through the enhancement of recreational and commercial fisheries. In regions such as Finland and Sweden, stocking has been central to maintaining fishing opportunities and supporting local economies (Salminen et al. 2007), especially following dam construction and habitat degradation (Vasemägi et al. 2005). Harrison et al. (2018) emphasizes that voluntary hatcheries supported by stocking can generate substantial local economic value, both through direct fishing-related revenue and by fostering cultural and symbolic connections to salmonid species. Moreover, stocking operations often serve as vehicles for public engagement, raising awareness about species conservation and mobilizing stakeholders to support broader management efforts (Bacon et al. 2015, NASCO 2024). Zink et al. (2023) highlights the creation of new recreational fishing opportunities as a key motivator for stocking, particularly when framed as a way to compensate for past environmental damage. Additionally, public perception surveys have shown that anglers who are highly invested in fishing tend to express stronger support for stocking initiatives, perceiving them as essential for sustaining fisheries (Perry et al. 2024).

However, the socio-economic impacts of stocking are not uniformly positive and can carry unintended consequences. Molony et al. (2003) warns that the apparent simplicity of stocking as a solution to declining fish abundance can obscure the underlying ecological problems, potentially leading stakeholders and policymakers to neglect habitat restoration in favor of short-term numerical gains. Harrison et al. (2018) and Kochalski et al. (2019) caution that this reliance on stocking may inadvertently reinforce the belief that human impacts on rivers can always be offset technologically, diminishing public urgency to address root causes like pollution or habitat fragmentation. Moreover, the financial costs of stocking programs can be substantial and are sometimes poorly justified when weighed against their long-term ecological outcomes, particularly when funds are diverted from habitat-based solutions (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). Social conflicts may also arise, as different stakeholder groups — such as conservation biologists, fisheries managers, and anglers — may hold competing views on what constitutes success, with some prioritizing wild population recovery and others focusing on catch rates (Perry et al. 2024). Fish conservation efforts based on charismatic species like Atlantic salmon may be particularly effective in countries such as Norway, where there is a strong economic and cultural connection to freshwater environments. In contrast, in France—where people tend to have a more abstract concern for nature—focusing conservation messaging on broader ecosystem values and the non-use benefits of fish is likely to garner greater public support (Kochalski et al. 2019). Among respondents from four countries (Norway, Sweden, Germany, and France), French participants showed the highest agreement with the view that native fish populations should primarily be managed for human benefit and that these populations are valuable only if people derive some use from them (Kochalski et al. 2019). Taken together, these insights underscore the importance of transparent communication, participatory governance, and rigorous socio-economic evaluation when designing stocking programs.

Overall, hatchery-reared salmon differ markedly from wild salmon in genotype, phenotype, be-

Figure 6.1: Overview of the primary ecological, genetic, and management impacts associated with Atlantic salmon stocking programs. ©C. Bouchard

havior, and life-history traits (Figure ??). These differences, combined with the direct effects of increasing local fish density, can have strong and unintended consequences on wild populations through density-dependent mechanisms, sanitary impacts, and genetic effects, among others. Additionally, managers' and stakeholders' decisions to implement stocking programs can have socio-economic repercussions that may further negatively affect the populations targeted by conservation plans. After reviewing the comparative biology of hatchery-reared and wild salmon and the *in natura* impacts of stocking on wild populations and the associated eco-evolutionary processes, the next section examines how stocking programs are currently evaluated and should be assessed, explaining why some stocking plans have had deleterious effects while others have been associated with positive outcomes.

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CHAPTER

7

Evaluations of programs: methods, successes, failures

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7.1. EVALUATION METHODS AND CHALLENGES

// 7.1.1 OVERALL CONSIDERATIONS

Evaluating stocking programs for Atlantic salmon is a complex task that requires consideration of ecological, genetic, and socio-economic factors. The question of how to evaluate stocking operations is not new. As early as Vibert (1945), the efficiency of stocking practices was questioned, highlighting the need to gather more knowledge. Later, Ritter (1997) emphasized the importance of better evaluating each stocking plan. Since then, several studies have contributed valuable insights and methodologies to improve our understanding and assessment of these programs.

The central issue in assessing a stocking program is whether it achieves its initial objectives without incurring excessive costs — not only economically, but, from our perspective, primarily ecologically since we are mainly interested in conservation programs. For example, Young (2013) suggested that the potential harm inflicted on wild salmon populations by stocking is not offset by measurable benefits to recreational fisheries. Therefore, the evaluation of a stocking program necessarily depends on its context and objectives. Conservation programs and fisheries enhancement programs should — and indeed must — not be evaluated using the same criteria. Despite this, most conservation stocking programs are assessed in a similar and often overly simplistic manner. Here, we review the evaluation methods used or proposed in numerous studies, as well as the challenges associated with these assessments.

// 7.1.2 SOCIOLOGY

A recent study nevertheless showed that anglers can be satisfied with stocking operations even if they have no access to any evidence of the effectiveness of these releases (Perry et al. 2024). Moreover, the authors found that management actions preferred by anglers were species-specific, and that anglers for whom fishing played a central role in their lives had a more favorable opinion of stocking than those for whom fishing was less central (Perry et al. 2024). These results contradict a previous study, which showed that anglers who considered fishing central to their lives were more experienced, had more developed knowledge of the environment, and therefore might have a different perspective on management operations than anglers for whom fishing was not central (Perry et al. 2024). This was notably the case for trout anglers in an earlier study, who viewed stocking operations negatively because they impacted the “purity”, implicitly referring to genetic integrity (Bryan 1977). However, more recent studies have shown the opposite — that is, a strong endorsement of stocking among specialized anglers (Arlinghaus and Mehner 2005, Slaton et al. 2023) — because it was anglers' beliefs and ecological knowledge, rather than their experience, that better predicted support for habitat restoration policies rather than stocking actions (Arlinghaus and Mehner 2005). Therefore, there is a significant challenge in identifying the risks, effects, and effectiveness of stocking operations, but above all, ensuring that this scientific knowledge is shared with the relevant stakeholders. Assessing how anglers and other users of the species (for cultural, societal, recreational, or other purposes) are involved is therefore necessary, as well as understanding how society participates in stocking programs. However, the public can also be engaged in many other measures to restore habitat and to share and transmit knowledge about the species. Thus, involving the public in stocking operations should not be used as a justification for implementing such programs.

// 7.1.3 DEMOGRAPHIC AND MODELING EVALUATION

Understanding the population dynamics of a targeted population is necessary to assess whether a conservation plan is required, whether conservation stocking is needed, and, if so, to evaluate the suitability and efficiency of the stocking operation (Lennox et al. 2021). However, in a recent study of over 2,000 Atlantic salmon populations, only 25% were assessed in terms of population dynamics through stock-recruitment relationships (Chaput 2012). This illustrates the lack of demographic knowledge for numerous Atlantic salmon populations. Without such knowledge, and when a stocking operation is in place, its evaluation from a demographic perspective cannot be properly conducted.

Concerning conservation stocking plans, such as those used in France, they occur, by definition, only at low stock levels. From a demographic perspective, if a plan is adequate, efficient, and effective, the expected result should be a clear and substantial increase in recruitment for fish populations exhibiting compensatory dynamics, such as Atlantic salmon (Bacon et al. 2015, Saavedra-Nieves et al. 2020). To be able to assess this, demography prior to the program should be well understood, and Biological Reference Points should be defined (Lennox et al. 2021).

Bacon et al. (2015) incorporated stock level into stock-recruitment relationships, highlighting that in species like salmon characterized by compensatory dynamics, stocking at low stock levels should lead to a clear and substantial increase in recruitment. This underscores the importance of considering ecological context when evaluating stocking outcomes. Modeling approaches have been applied to separate natural and stocked juvenile densities, as demonstrated by Dauphin et al. (2017) in the Allier River, even when stocked fish are unmarked.

Modeling population dynamics is necessary, as shown by Legault (2005), since population viability analyses indicated that excessive stocking during periods of good marine survival can paradoxically increase extinction risk by limiting population resilience. Bayesian modeling approaches, as demonstrated by Dauphin et al. (2017) and Barton et al. (2020), offer promising tools to improve management decisions, including assessing dam removal impacts on populations and evaluating stocking scenarios. Another promising approach involves demo-genetic tools that link demography, genetics, and management decisions (Folio et al. 2024; 2021, Lamarins et al. 2022a;b).

// 7.1.4 DATA ACQUISITION

Early evaluations, such as those by Gayou and Roguet (1996), estimated juvenile densities and recapture rates, revealing that increasing stocking densities could paradoxically reduce apparent survival rates, illustrating the complexity of interpreting monitoring data. However, Gayou and Roguet (1996) also noted a lack of resources for conducting thorough evaluations of stocking effectiveness, a concern echoed by Bousquet (1996), who highlighted limitations in assessment methods that relied solely on stock structure comparisons without direct links to stocking.

More refined techniques, such as double marking with cryomarking and fin clipping, were em-

ployed by Dumas (1979) to compare growth and sex ratios between hatchery and wild fish, providing detailed survival and performance data. Marking techniques and cohort assignment facilitate evaluation without broodstock samples, as shown by Hagen et al. (2021). Currently, several individual tagging methods are available, including DNA parentage analysis, coded wire tagging (CWT), passive integrated transponder (PIT) tagging, radio tagging, and acoustic tagging, which provide individual-level insights on behavior, migration routes, and reproductive success. These individual data can complement group-level data acquired through fin clipping or visible implant elastomer (VIE) tagging. Fish tracking is essential for survival estimates (Serrano et al. 2009). Juvenile density assessments post-stocking have been used effectively in various contexts, including studies by Prignon et al. (1999) and Wallace and Curry (2017).

Trushenski et al. (2015) outlined practical recommendations for robust evaluation, including marking both hatchery and wild fish, experimentally varying stocking levels, monitoring recruitment and fishing mortality, and assessing reproductive performance using genetic tools. Their work also highlighted the Hatchery Scientific Review Group's (HSRG) modeling of hatchery fish proportions in spawning escapements and broodstock composition, notably applied in Columbia River populations. Recent studies, such as Moncayo et al. (2024) and Matte et al. (2024), emphasize the need to monitor survival and recruitment dynamics before and after stocking to understand changes in the population production. Similarly, Radinger et al. (2023) advocated for the use of Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) experimental designs to robustly assess ecosystem-level effects of stocking.

// 7.1.5 GOING BEYOND ABUNDANCE

Critiques of common evaluation approaches were presented by Glover et al. (2018), who argued that abundance indicators alone are insufficient, as natural regulatory mechanisms and spatio-temporal processes are often overlooked. They proposed modeling approaches that integrate natural egg and juvenile production with stocking contributions while accounting for monitoring biases and environmental variability.

Improving natural reproduction conditions can enhance survival probabilities, as shown by Saltveit (2006), making the monitoring of natural reproduction mandatory. Stocking efficacy depends on habitat accessibility and quality, as noted by Van Puijenbroek et al. (2019) and Thorstad et al. (2021), who stressed the importance of smolt condition and habitat restoration. Sediment quality and habitat alterations further complicate outcomes (Lennox et al. 2021). Therefore, monitoring habitat quality and restoration is also essential to better evaluate stocking programs. For instance, modeling of smolt migration losses over decades in the Penobscot river reveals significant mortality at dams, with only a fraction of stocked smolts reaching the ocean (Stevens et al. 2019).

The question of what constitutes a “good” salmon — whether one that is reproductively successful and harvestable or one that reflects wild genetic and ecological characteristics — was discussed by Harrison and Berseth (2024), who emphasized the need to reflect on conservation goals in rapidly changing environments. Thus, the question is not only how many salmon are in the populations but which salmon. Phenological and ontogenetic considerations, including match-mismatch dynamics and readiness to cope with environmental perturbations, are important for evaluating stocking success

(Bailey et al. 2010). This necessitates understanding the phenotype, behavior, and phenology of wild salmon prior to stocking and monitoring these traits during and after the stocking program.

// 7.1.6 GENETIC ASSESSMENTS

We have already reviewed the numerous risks of deleterious genetic effects of stocking programs on wild populations, highlighting the necessity of implementing adequate assessments. Genetic evaluations are particularly relevant for species with low genetic diversity and small population sizes (Roques et al. 2018). For instance, Almodóvar et al. (2020) documented genetic deterioration in the River Sella population due to stocking, including allele loss, introgression, and reduced effective population size, underscoring the risks associated with genetic impacts. Well-monitored programs, such as the one described by García-Vega et al. (2025), provide valuable case studies for best practices, especially regarding genetic considerations. Notably, the Bidasoa stocking program is among the most thoroughly monitored, providing essential data to evaluate the program both genetically and demographically. Genetic introgression assessments must incorporate sex-specific markers to avoid underestimation, as males may mature early in hatcheries without marine survival (Gabián and Morán 2019).

// 7.1.7 ECOLOGICAL AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC RISKS

Evaluating ecological risks beyond target species is crucial. Pearsons and Hopley (1999) provided a framework to assess the impacts of stocked species on native communities, emphasizing risks related to competition, predation, and disease transmission. The authors listed five key tasks required to perform an ecological risk assessment: determining nontarget taxa (NTT) objectives; determining or hypothesizing spatial-temporal overlap of target taxa with NTT life stages; determining or hypothesizing strong ecological interactions; assessing ecological risk for each NTT; and determining scientific uncertainty (Pearsons and Hopley 1999).

Cost-benefit analyses reveal that the financial costs of stocking often outweigh the benefits, especially when stocking is used to compensate for dam impacts (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). In their study, the authors also demonstrated a mismatch between the geographical distribution of benefits and the corresponding rearing and release costs, since salmon are caught along their migration routes rather than where they were released as compensation for dams. Socio-economic evaluations, such as those by Harrison et al. (2018), provide additional dimensions to assessment by investigating psychological and social benefits of stocking. Stocking programs may also be assessed using network analyses to evaluate whether all actors and structures involved in the program interact effectively (Flye et al. 2021). When stocking programs are designed to support both consumptive (harvest angling) and non-consumptive (catch-and-release angling) recreational fishing, the recreational fishing opportunities created by stocking must be discussed and evaluated, as argued by Zink et al. (2023).

While program evaluation should be central, it is often lacking in most programs. Pearsons et al. (2012) provided a good example of an evaluation conducted prior to a future program. They combined literature reviews, expert opinion (Delphi method), and mathematical modeling to conduct ecological risk assessments of hatchery impacts. Their study concluded that while hatchery programs aim to support fish populations and fisheries, they can pose significant ecological risks to wild fish through

competition, predation, disease transmission, and genetic interactions. The authors emphasize the need for careful management and monitoring of hatchery programs to mitigate these risks and protect wild fish populations.

Together, these studies illustrate the multifaceted challenges and methodologies involved in evaluating Atlantic salmon stocking programs, emphasizing the need for integrative, context-specific, and adaptive approaches. To perform a rigorous and comprehensive evaluation, as proposed by Molony et al. (2003) (Figure 7.1), numerous data are necessary before, during, and after the program.

Figure 3. Proposed flow chart expanding on the steps in Figure 2. Note that the ability to produce fish in a hatchery is not driving the decision making process. However, appropriate husbandry and hatchery protocols are important considerations.

Figure 7.1: Flow-chart for the evaluation of each program proposed by Molony et al. (2003).

7.2. AVOIDING THE PITFALLS OF ASSESSMENT: DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN STOCKING AND RESTORATION

Here we review some programs viewed as either success or failure by authors of previous studies. Thus, the same program can appear in both the success and failure subsections. In the failure subsection, we also include all plans leading to “no effect”, since even if there are no detrimental effects, the fact that the stocking program does not improve the demography of the population constitutes a failure.

Recently, two scientific articles reviewed restoration and conservation programs targeting Atlantic salmon populations for which assessments have been made (Lennox et al. 2021, McMillan et al. 2023). The review by McMillan et al. (2023) **was not focused solely on Atlantic salmon but on salmonids** (*Oncorhynchus*, *Salmo*, *Salvelinus*, and *Thymallus* species) in North America, Europe, and Asia, and considered all potential effects (not only demographic). Among the 207 studies they retained, 144 (70%) reported adverse effects on wild salmonids and 26 (13%) reported minimally adverse effects. Only seven (3%) publications reported beneficial effects of hatchery programs on wild salmonids (McMillan et al. 2023). Specifically for Atlantic salmon, 15 out of 19 publications reported adverse effects (13 adverse and 2 minimally adverse). The effects evaluated by these studies are usually genetic or ecological. Importantly, concerning hatchery programs aiming at population recovery, 30% had adverse or minimally adverse effects, while 29% had beneficial effects.

Lennox et al. (2021) provided a recent review of 95 Atlantic salmon population restoration programs for which evaluations were available in 49 peer-reviewed papers. They qualified three levels of success: self-sustaining wild population (level 1), robust self-sustaining population (level 2), and harvestable surplus (level 3). This again highlights the necessity of understanding population dynamics before, during, and after the program, defining biological reference points, and collecting necessary data.

Among the 95 restoration programs evaluated, 39 reached level 1 success, none reached level 2, 26 reached level 3, and 18 did not reach any level of success (Lennox et al. 2021). Restoration programs that reached level 3 success targeted habitat and water quality improvement and dam removal (Lennox et al. 2021). Only 19 studies reported stocking operations within a restoration program. Among those 19 studies, **only two achieved any level of success** (Lennox et al. 2021). These successes correspond to programs reported by Perrier et al. (2014) and Saltveit et al. (2019). We will discuss these in the following subsection.

// 7.2.1 EVALUATING RESTOCKING PROGRAMS: WHEN ATTRIBUTED SUCCESSES ARE ACTUALLY DUE TO ECOLOGICAL RESTORATION

/// 7.2.1.1 BASSIN DE L'ADOUR - FRANCE

The program qualified as a success in Lennox et al. (2021) was described in Perrier et al. (2014). The study focused on genetic processes in the *Adour catchment* in France, located at the southern edge of the species' distribution range, following habitat restoration and stocking. The authors sampled juveniles in several sub-drainages, including the *Nivelle*, the *Nive*, the *Saison*, the *Gave d'Oloron*, the

Gave d'Aspe, the *Gave d'Ossau*, and the *Gave de Pau*. Some of these sub-drainages, or the sub-drainages themselves, had been recently colonized or recolonized after habitat restoration (e.g., dam equipped with fish ladder; Perrier et al. (2014)). The authors found that genetic diversity (expected heterozygosity and allelic richness) was similar between continuously inhabited sites and recolonized sites, but the effective population size (N_e) was lower in the recolonized sites. They also observed low admixture and low proportions of putative migrants or hybrids within continuously inhabited sites, suggesting a relatively low impact of stocking (Perrier et al. 2014). In fact, the authors suggested that the use of geographically and genetically distant populations to stock rivers within the Adour catchment may have resulted in noticeable admixture and a local homogenization of genetic diversity (Perrier et al. 2014). Therefore, the overall success of the restoration was achieved primarily through the improvement of dam crossing and habitat restoration (Perrier et al. 2014). This program is not a stocking success.

/// 7.2.1.2 SULDALSLÅGEN - NORWAY

The second success reported by Lennox et al. (2021) was described by Saltveit et al. (2019) and concerns the river *Suldalslågen* in Norway. Dam construction for hydropower production led to an estimated annual loss of 20,000 smolts. To compensate for this loss, a stocking program was launched, initially with parr and later with smolts (Saltveit 2006). A first evaluation of this program was conducted by Saltveit (2006), who concluded that there was a lack of positive response to stocking. The explanations for this lack of positive effect included the smaller size and later migration timing of hatchery-reared smolts compared to wild smolts. During the program, between 160,000 and 250,000 one-summer-old fish were stocked annually, but only between 6 and 10 individuals ($\leq 0.005\%$) were recaptured as adults in the river. In the later study by Saltveit et al. (2019), the program was evaluated based on the number of large salmon caught by fishermen (salmon heavier than 7 kg). The authors found that before 2011, the catch of large salmon was dominated by wild fish (i.e., from natural reproduction), whereas after 2011, the proportions of wild and hatchery-reared fish were similar. The improvement observed in recent years in the number of large salmon caught by anglers appears to be due to a combination of water management and stocking (Saltveit et al. 2019). Water management was targeted to increase the number of large salmon catchable by anglers, and stocking seems to have contributed to this goal, leading to a potential success in terms of that objective. However, juvenile production, total abundance, and diversity (both genetic and phenotypic), as assessed by Saltveit (2006), were not evaluated in the later study. Available evidence indicates that the only demonstrated benefit of stocking pertains to *fisheries management* (e.g., supporting recreational fishing), rather than the *conservation of wild populations*.

/// 7.2.1.3 ELBE - GERMANY

Another emblematic example is the case of the river Elbe in Germany. Atlantic salmon vanished from all large German river catchments in the mid-20th century. In November 1994, a working group on “Elbe Fisheries”, gathering all fisheries authorities, established a stocking program to reintroduce Atlantic salmon into the river. The stocking program was launched in November 1994, and more than 3.8 million salmon were stocked between 1994 and spring 2003 (Wolter 2015). In a tributary, more than 755,000 salmon were stocked between 1999 and 2010. The Elbe stocking program is usually

considered a success due to the recolonization of the river by Atlantic salmon. However, as noted by the authors, “none of the mentioned projects for salmon reintroduction has a benchmark on how much returning adults are needed for a self-sustaining salmon population and later on for a salmon stock which allows fisheries use” (Wolter 2015). The current number of 300–400 returning adults is well below the historical harvest and the potential target stock size of between 4,000 and 10,000 salmon. The success of the program could be viewed as having “primed the pump”, similar to the Adour catchment. However, the contribution of natural recolonization is unknown, and this program, like that of the Adour catchment, has relied heavily on habitat quality improvements and dam removal. The authors also suggested that further improvements require a catchment-wide approach to better include upstream spawning areas; otherwise, “the reintroduction program of salmon in the River Elbe might fail to attain the critical effective population size for a self-sustaining salmon population with its option for future fisheries use”.

/// 7.2.1.4 THE DANISH CASE: WHEN STOCKING GIVES WAY TO HABITAT RESTORATION

Restoration programs in Danish rivers (Storå, Skjern, Varde, Ribe) are **frequently misrepresented** as evidence of stocking effectiveness (Koed et al. 2020). A retrospective analysis, however, reveals a more complex reality :

1. Historical context and initial failure (early 20th century)

These river systems experienced *population collapse* in the early 1900s, primarily due to :

- **widespread habitat destruction** (channelization, urbanization),
- **massive dam construction** blocking migrations.

2. Sporadic stocking period (1950--1980)

Non-systematic stocking operations were conducted for three decades, **without significant population improvement** (Koed et al. 2020). 1990s assessments did, however, reveal :

- **persistence of natural reproduction** despite decline,
- **maintained local genetic diversity** in certain sections (e.g., Storå),
- **ineffectiveness of stocking alone** for stock recovery.

3. Paradigm shift (1990s--2000s)

Facing these findings, managers **radically revised their strategy**, by :

- **abandoning stocking** as a central tool (from the 2000s onward),
- **prioritizing habitat restoration** :

- removal of **73 dams** (Table 7.1),
- installation of **28 fish passes** and protective screens,
- **rehabilitation of 349 spawning sites** (gravel/substrate addition),
- **strengthening legislative frameworks** :
 - fishing bans in fjords (Nissum, Ringkøbing),
 - establishment of **minimum demographic thresholds** for population viability.

4. Outcomes and key lessons

- **Relative success** : Stocks show *positive trends* since the 2000s, but authors emphasize the need for **continued efforts**, particularly to :
 - complete remaining dam removals,
 - improve juvenile habitat quality (Koed et al. 2020).
- **Marginal role of stocking** : Data do not allow assessment of its actual contribution to reproduction or population production. Its use is now **restricted to a supportive tool**, provided that :
 - habitat **carrying capacity** is not exceeded,
 - **structural issues** (dams, predation, pollution) are addressed upstream.
- **Acknowledged fisheries objective** : as noted by Koed et al. (2020), these programs also included a *fisheries dimension*, highlighting that “success” criteria may reflect **socio-economic priorities** rather than **ecological indicators**.

Table 7.1: Comparison of management strategies in different river systems in Denmark, adapted from Koed et al. (2020).

System	Management strategies
River Storå	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat restoration of 60 sites (100–2 500 m²) : adding gravels/rocks • 15 dams removed • Ban of fishing in the fjord Nissum
River Skjern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat restoration of 98 sites (100–2 500 m²) • 41 dams removed • Ban of fishing in the fjord Ringkøbing
River Varde	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Habitat restoration of 191 sites (100–2 500 m²) • 17 dams removed

/// 7.2.1.5 ULLA - SPAIN

Saavedra-Nieves et al. (2020) studied the restoration program in the *river Ulla* in Spain. The river is 132 km long, but only 80 km are accessible to Atlantic salmon, and a fish trap located 40 km upstream from the river mouth enables monitoring of adult returns. A supportive breeding program based on artificial spawning began in 2000 and was still ongoing in 2021 (Saavedra-Nieves et al. 2020). Hatchery-reared parr released in autumn had their adipose fins clipped, allowing stakeholders to distinguish between wild and hatchery-reared fish at the fish trap. The authors assessed the restoration program using a long-term dataset (1992–2018) of adult returns at the fish trap. This monitoring enabled a Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) evaluation. They found a gradual increase in adult returns up to the early 1990s (before stocking), followed by a stable period until 2007. A break-point was identified in 2007, after which adult returns increased, particularly with more multi-sea-winter (MSW) fish caught. Wild fish represented 82.70% of returns from 2000 to 2018, a proportion not significantly different from the period 1992–1999. The authors concluded that the increase in returning adults in the Ulla River is due not only to salmon stocking but mostly to conservation practices, especially improved connectivity, since the break-point corresponds to the construction of a vertical ladder downstream of the fish trap.

/// 7.2.1.6 THAMES & SEINE - ENGLAND & FRANCE

Two other rivers supporting Atlantic salmon populations are also usually viewed as successes of salmon restoration programs: the *river Seine* in France and the *river Thames* in England. Salmon was extirpated from the Thames in 1833. Several stocking programs attempted to restore the population without success. After significant improvements in water quality, a salmon was caught downstream of London in 1974 (Griffiths et al. 2011). Following this, stocking of juveniles began in 1975, mostly

using salmon originating from a Scottish hatchery (Griffiths et al. 2011). The number of adult returns increased, reaching a peak of 338 individuals in 1993 (Griffiths et al. 2011). In 1994, a restoration program targeted one major tributary of the Thames with the largest amount of breeding and nursery habitat (Griffiths et al. 2011). However, since 1997, the number of adult returns decreased, reaching a low in 2005 with no salmon caught (Griffiths et al. 2011). Sixteen adults caught between 2005 and 2008 were genetically assigned (Griffiths et al. 2011). The authors found that all but one individual were assigned to rivers in southern England, suggesting that these individuals were not stocked but were strays from other rivers (Griffiths et al. 2011). Overall, the stocking program in the Thames may have also “primed the pump”, having a positive short-term effect, but resulting in no or negative effects in the long term, as abundance decreased and most adult returns originated from straying individuals (Griffiths et al. 2011).

The river Seine provides a clear example of how habitat restoration can lead to the recolonization of a river by Atlantic salmon. Salmon vanished from the river at the end of the 19th century, and only some unsuccessful stocking operations were performed during that century (Perrier et al. 2010). Water quality improvements began in the early 1990s, and in 2008, 162 adults were recorded on video at the Poses dam. Seven of these fish had their adipose fins clipped, suggesting a low proportion of stocked individuals. The authors conducted genetic analyses on seven individuals caught by anglers between 2001 and 2008. Two individuals were assigned to foreign origins, one of which had the adipose fin clipped (Perrier et al. 2010). The other individuals were assigned to French populations, including one assigned to the French Allier population, which is characterized by the longest upstream migration (Perrier et al. 2010). Overall, the authors suggested that the natural recolonization of the Seine River results from general water quality improvements.

/// 7.2.1.7 SAINT MARYS - CANADA

In 2012, natural reproduction of Atlantic salmon was detected for the first time in the river *Saint Marys* in Michigan. Atlantic salmon have been annually stocked with 25,000–30,000 pre-smolts for decades in the Upper Great Lakes, to which the river is connected (Tucker et al. 2014). The stocking program was successful in its primary objectives: it created a stable recreational fishery generated from hatchery-reared fish (Tucker et al. 2014). Due to the presence of other salmonids in the Great Lakes, Atlantic salmon juveniles are known to shift to alternative prey, leading to a hypothesized thiamine deficiency as the main cause of Early Mortality Syndrome (EMS) in the Great Lakes (Tucker et al. 2014). However, after 25 years of smolt stocking, the first natural reproduction was observed (Tucker et al. 2014).

/// 7.2.1.8 RIVER TYNE - ENGLAND

The River Tyne is one of the most well-documented examples of perceived stocking success. Located in northeastern England, the river experienced severely depleted salmon runs during the 1950s, primarily due to estuarine pollution from industrial and urban sewage discharge (Milner et al. 2008). A comprehensive restoration program subsequently led to reduced industrial activity and significant improvements in water quality (Milner et al. 2008).

However, in the 1980s, construction of a dam on the North Tyne - one of the river's main tributaries - resulted in the loss of 220,000 m² of critical salmon rearing habitat (Milner et al. 2008). This environmental impact necessitated a mitigation agreement that included the establishment of a hatchery and stocking program to compensate for the habitat loss. Initiated in 1978, the program primarily released 0+ juveniles (with a smaller proportion of 1+ individuals, Milner et al. 2008).

Between 1983 and 2000, stocked salmon were tagged with coded wire tags (CWT), enabling researchers to track adult returns and estimate the relative contributions of hatchery-reared versus naturally produced individuals to the spawning population (Milner et al. 2008). The program also included monitoring of juvenile abundance and water quality throughout its duration.

A subsequent study investigated the relative contributions of **natural processes** (including straying, natural reproduction, and recolonization) and **stocking efforts** to the observed population recovery. The authors concluded that **natural processes were the primary drivers** of recovery (Milner et al. 2008). Their conclusions were supported by several key observations:

- The majority of spawning escapement consistently consisted of wild fish (based on CWT data),
- The presence of moderate juvenile stocks in the late 1970s, prior to stocking initiation,
- The temporal alignment between water quality improvements and the recovery of catch rates and fishing effort,
- The recovery of catch and effort metrics predating hatchery returns,
- The simultaneous recovery of sea trout populations in the same system.

Nevertheless, the study also acknowledged that stocking may have played a relative role in accelerating and stabilizing the early stages of population recovery, particularly during periods when water quality improvements were still inconsistent (Milner et al. 2008).

/// 7.2.1.9 OTHERS

An older review than those of McMillan et al. (2023) and Lennox et al. (2021) examined three early successes of Atlantic salmon stocking programs (Ritter 1997). Interestingly, the authors already provided recommendations to conduct efficient stocking programs or at least reduce the potential negative impacts of stocking hatchery-reared fish. One success was the program above *Grand Falls* (Exploits River), where between 2,000 and 5,000 adults were counted annually from 1980 to 1992, supporting the stocking of more than one million fry each year. Adult returns peaked at 11,395 in 1996, likely due to a moratorium on commercial fishing, as hypothesized by the authors (Ritter 1997). Another success presented by Ritter (1997) was the *Torrent River*, where a fishway was constructed in 1966 to allow passage over natural falls located 3 km upstream of the head of the tide. After the fishway was built, 738 grilse were stocked from 1972 to 1976 (Ritter 1997). Adult returns increased from about 50 in the late 1960s to 2,000 in the 1980s (Ritter 1997). The third success was the river LaHave, where the restoration program included both fishway construction and stocking. A fishway

was built 15 km above the head of tide, and both hatchery-reared parr and smolts were stocked above the newly built fishway starting in 1971. Following these efforts, adult returns from natural spawning increased rapidly to about 2,000 fish.

// 7.2.2 FAILURES OF CONSERVATION STOCKING OPERATIONS

Most stocking programs concerning Atlantic salmon, notably those aimed at conservation, restoration, or compensation, are not successful; most have no effect or are even deleterious (Lennox et al. 2021).

/// 7.2.2.1 NORWAY

In Norway, despite extensive stocking programs involving different stages of juvenile salmon, the targeted populations have continued to decline (Saltveit 2006). The authors found that stocking salmon in Norwegian rivers does not lead to increased yields. They also observed higher mortality at sea for hatchery-reared smolts, probably due to their smaller size, younger age, and later migration (Saltveit 2006). The authors argued that stocking can only be effective if natural reproduction is below the carrying capacity, and they found that stocked fish represented only a small proportion of anglers' catches (2.7% to 18.9%) despite the stocking effort. They concluded that their results strongly indicate the benefits of improving conditions for natural reproduction, as wild smolts have a much higher probability of survival at sea (Saltveit 2006).

/// 7.2.2.2 RHINE - GERMANY

One emblematic and contemporary example is the *river Rhine*. Atlantic salmon was extirpated from the River Rhine during the 1950s, mainly due to water quality issues (i.e., pollution) and dams (Ingendhal and Beeck 2011). Spawning grounds are located mostly in Germany and, to a lesser extent, in France, in the Bruche and Lauter tributaries (Van Rijssel et al. 2024). In Switzerland, while some spawning grounds are available, they are difficult to access (Van Rijssel et al. 2024). To enable the reestablishment of an Atlantic salmon population, a stocking program was launched, and between one and three million juvenile salmon were stocked each year from 1998 to 2009 (Ingendhal and Beeck 2011, Schneider 2011, Van Rijssel et al. 2024). Despite this substantial stocking effort, and the use of salmon as a flagship species, the estimated spawning population remains low, between 350 and 800 individuals, with only a small proportion of the genetic origins participating in reproduction (Van Rijssel et al. 2024). The authors found very high percentages of salmon disappearing during both upstream and downstream migrations, with, for instance, 74% of adults disappearing in the lower Rhine and 71% for smolts (Van Rijssel et al. 2024). At one power station, an additional mortality of 16-25% for smolts was observed. Losses in the river are much higher than at sea, and the authors suggested that numerous ecological restoration actions still need to be implemented along the river course, which is highly modified by shipping and regulated by dams (Van Rijssel et al. 2024).

/// 7.2.2.3 ADOUR BASIN - FRANCE

In France, stocking has been used on the river system *Adour*, especially on the *Nive* river and *Nivelle* river, as previously stated in the subsection on success, where we discussed the success of the restoration program, not the stocking program. As mentioned earlier (Perrier et al. 2014), Bousquet (1996) argued that the increase in adult returns was due to dam removal and the opening of upstream spawning grounds, not the stocking program. In addition, Perrier et al. (2014) found a positive correlation between the number of adult returns and the number of 1SW salmon caught by anglers. However, the number of 1SW salmon caught was negatively associated with natural recruitment. Thus, an increase in the number of adult returns was associated with a decrease in natural recruitment (Bousquet 1996). Overall, the authors suggested that stocking may have increased the number of adult returns, but these returns increased fishing pressure and supported the fishery rather than natural reproduction (Bousquet 1996). Such a result is typically the aim of a fisheries enhancement stocking program, but definitely not a conservation stocking program.

The case of the river *Nivelle* is particularly interesting because the river is short, and before 1984, the accessible section extended only 4.5 km upstream from the saltwater limit (Dumas and Marty 1987). The river has been stocked since 1962 (Dumas et al. 1979). Neveu (1981) found that hatchery-reared parr constituted 21% of the parr caught in the *Nivelle*, and the salmon density was lower than the density measured before stocking (Neveu 1981). Already in 1981, the authors hypothesized that the lack of success of the stocking program was probably due to increased density-dependent processes resulting from the addition of hatchery-reared salmon in the river (Neveu 1981). In a subsequent study, the authors found that hatchery-reared individuals represented between 18% and 82% of annual adult returns over nine years of monitoring (Dumas and Marty 1987). Regular stocking ceased in the 1990s, while in 1984 and again in the 1990s, two fishways were built to increase the accessible habitat for salmon. The increase in adult returns has been mostly associated with the opening of spawning grounds in the *Nivelle* (Dumas 1979, Dumas and Marty 1987). In October 2023, a dam was removed, making the upstream part of the *Nivelle*, above the Spanish border, accessible. Only three months later, adult salmon were observed in the newly accessible section, where salmon had disappeared more than 100 years ago due to dams.

/// 7.2.2.4 GARONNE DORDOGNE - FRANCE

On the French rivers *Garonne* and *Dordogne*, salmon were extirpated in 1906 (Gayou and Roguet 1996). In 1940, some stocking operations were carried out on the *Garonne* with juveniles produced from adults caught in the river *Adour* (Gayou and Roguet 1996). These stocking operations led to the capture of adults by a fishery at Toulouse, but in 1971 the Golfech dam was built. In 1975, a first restoration program was launched on the *Dordogne*, followed by a similar program in 1980 on the *Garonne* (Gayou and Roguet 1996). The two restoration programs aimed to improve habitat connectivity, increase knowledge of population productivity, perform stocking operations, and protect species and their habitats through new legislation and public outreach. The program found that 294 weirs and dams impeded natural migration towards spawning areas, and the decision was made to build fishways at the largest dams (Gayou and Roguet 1996). Overall, the number of adult returns increased in 1992 and reached a first peak in 1994, probably because the decision was made to use only French salmon for broodstock and to stock smolts downstream of the lowest dams on both rivers (Gayou

and Roguet 1996). While these stocking procedures were amplified, a sharp drop in the number of adult returns was observed in 1995, notably on the Dordogne. After that, a peak was observed in 2000-2002 on both rivers, then levels returned to levels comparable to 1994 (COGEPOMI GDCSL 2021). Overall, these programs enabled the return of salmon to these rivers, but not the establishment of stable and viable populations, especially on the Garonne (Gayou and Roguet 1996).

/// 7.2.2.5 GIRNOCK BURN - SCOTLAND

The *Girnock Burn* catchment in Scotland offers another good example of a stocking program that did not succeed, despite being well-designed and highly monitored (Bacon et al. 2015). In this program, a “descending” trap and an “ascending” trap were used to monitor adult returns and smolt escapement. Local adults caught at the ascending trap were used for stocking, and no stocking occurred before the launch of the monitoring program. The number of females used for stocking varied each year but was always known, as was the proportion of stocked ova relative to the total number of ova in the river. The ova from each female were divided into 10 batches, each fertilized by a different male, including precocious male parr (Bacon et al. 2015). The available males were rotated among females to maximize the number of males siring juveniles (Bacon et al. 2015). After fertilization, the 10 batches from each female were recombined into a single total batch. Such a fertilization plan is rare, especially with the use of precocious males. Egg batches were placed into separate baskets (one per female), each with several layers of eggs and gravel, in a raceway incubator. When the ova reached the eyed stage of development, the batches of live ova were amalgamated and mixed to ensure that offspring from all females would be distributed throughout the stream. Ova were then placed into plastic tubs (500 ova per tub), buried in separate shallow holes and covered with a shallow layer of substrate (Bacon et al. 2015). The plastic tubs allowed the eggs to remain inside, but enabled alevins to emerge through holes. Population dynamics were modeled using Beverton-Holt and Ricker stock-recruitment curves, which were modified to model demographic parameters as functions of the proportion of ova that were stocked and the number of ova in the previous cohort (to account for competition among cohorts). The authors found strong intercohort competition, with large cohorts reducing the survival rates of subsequent cohorts (Bacon et al. 2015). While this stocking program was well-designed to maximize genetic diversity and reduce domestication, the authors found no effect of stocking (Bacon et al. 2015). In another evaluation, Glover et al. (2018) found an increase in fry produced at stocking sites, but not in parr production, suggesting no overall benefit of stocking.

/// 7.2.2.6 MIRAMICHI - CANADA

Similar results have been found in the river *Miramichi* in Canada, where Atlantic salmon were stocked from 2006 to 2011 at the fry stage. Electrofishing was used to assess the efficiency of stocking operations in terms of parr production. It was found that parr densities were lower at stocked sites, probably due to an increase in downstream movements (Wallace and Curry 2017). Densities of parr also showed no response in the year following stocking, suggesting that stocking failed to increase parr density at the studied sites (Wallace and Curry 2017).

/// 7.2.2.7 BIDASOA - SPAIN

In Spain, several rivers have been stocked and monitored to evaluate, at least in part, stocking efficiency. In the *Bidasoa*, a well-documented stocking program, stocked salmon (fry and parr) exhibited a very low return rate (less than 1%, García-Vega et al. 2025). In the fish trap used to capture adults during upstream migration, 30% of salmon were hatchery-reared (García-Vega et al. 2025). While this stocking program aimed to maintain sufficient genetic diversity by partially renewing the broodstock each year, 1155 adult salmon have been caught for this broodstock (García-Vega et al. 2025). In comparison, the monitoring stations identified 2814 returns of stocked salmon (García-Vega et al. 2025). Overall, the population has been decreasing in recent years. Numerous dams are still present in the river, and the efficiency of the fishways has not been assessed but a Life European project (Life KANTAURIBAI) is assessing the cumulative impact of dams on downstream migration of smolts (pers. data).

/// 7.2.2.8 SELLA - SPAIN

On the river *Sella*, which supports one of the largest populations in Spain, returns were targeted by recreational fishing and declined in the mid-1970s (Almodóvar et al. 2020). In Spain, salmon exhibit a reduction in average size and age of returning adults, a delay in river entry, changes in genetic structure, and a reduction in the river area used by the species (Almodóvar et al. 2020). As in the Bidasoa, all salmon rivers are stocked with alevins from local fish farms, while between the 1970s and 1990s, fertilized eggs from Scotland were used (Almodóvar et al. 2020). Stocking led to an erosion of genetic diversity among Spanish populations, with the disappearance of native alleles and evidence of introgression of Scottish non-native alleles. For the Sella river, deterioration includes loss of native and distinctive alleles, introgression, and a reduction in the number of breeders and effective population size (Almodóvar et al. 2020). The very low effective population size found in contemporary samples represents a severe risk for the conservation of native salmon (Almodóvar et al. 2020), and echoes the discussion of wilderness and the type of salmon conservation programs that should be prioritized. Across 177 Spanish sites over a recent 10-year period (2010--2019), natural reproduction of Atlantic salmon was still present at only 20% of sites. At these sites, stocking programs failed to promote natural reproduction and could even hinder the persistence of natural populations. Evaluations of habitat quality, especially regarding dams and pollution, are lacking and need to be conducted (Soto et al. 2023).

/// 7.2.2.9 ENGLAND & WALES

Young (2013) conducted an evaluation of stocking in England and Wales across 62 rivers over 15 years. They quantified the relationship between stocking effort and angler catch statistics. They found that the 42 rivers with stocking had a non-significantly lower mean catch compared to the 20 rivers without stocking. For the stocked rivers, they found no evidence of a positive relationship between annual stocking efforts and catch statistics (Young 2013). The authors suggested that the potential damage inflicted on wild populations by stocking (such as deleterious effects on genetic diversity, phenotypic changes, etc.) is not balanced by any detectable benefits to fisheries. This finding is consistent with results from the Sella and Cares catchments, where the contribution of hatchery-reared salmon to recreational catches was actually higher in rivers where fewer juveniles were stocked, while each

hatchery-reared individual carries a high economic cost (Horreo et al. 2012). Thus, this high economic cost does not translate into increased opportunities for anglers, and hatchery-reared salmon may have deleterious effects on wild populations.

Globally, only a few stocking programs are qualified as successful, and most are usually unsuccessful — a pattern observed for numerous fish species (Brown and Day 2002). Moreover, successes are often defined solely by the number of adult returns. The extent to which these adults participate in reproduction, produce juveniles, and contribute to genetic and phenotypic diversity is rarely, if ever, investigated. The case described by Bousquet (1996) perfectly illustrates this point, with an increase in returns observed without any corresponding increase in natural reproduction. Thus, so-called successes are not truly successful in demographic terms and may still have adverse long-term effects (which are more difficult to quantify) on the genetics and local adaptation of populations.

In addition, most of the so-called “successful” programs included a strong component of habitat restoration (e.g., habitat connectivity, dam removal, riverbed and spawning habitat improvement, water quality enhancement, etc.; Lennox et al. 2021). This suggests that a successful program can only be achieved if the major threats are identified and addressed, there is political will to resolve these issues, and a core or remnant population still exhibits sufficient genetic diversity. In such rare cases, stocking may serve as a starting point or provide a temporary boost for only several years mitigating against extinction from demographic stochasticity (Griffiths et al. 2011, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Ritter 1997, Wolter 2015). However, the medium and long-term effects and fitness costs remain unknown (Lorenzen et al. 2012).

17.3. WHEN DOES STOCKING ACTUALLY WORK?

The few conservation-focused stocking programs with demonstrated success are exemplified by the three case studies analyzed by Ritter (1997) and in a less extent by the case of the river Tyne. These cases suggest that stocking *may* accelerate the recolonization of new habitats **provided it is combined with ambitious habitat improvement measures**. Yet, quantifying its *actual contribution* to these outcomes remains methodologically challenging, if not impossible to disentangle from confounding factors.

Conversely, in major restoration programs such as those conducted in the Thames or Seine rivers, stocking proved **ineffective** in boosting population numbers. Observed recoveries were solely attributable to **habitat quality enhancements** and **natural recolonization** (Griffiths et al. 2011, Perrier et al. 2010).

Lastly, a review of programs where stocking was implemented alongside other measures - as in Danish rivers (Koed et al. 2020) - further supports this pattern : **no positive contribution** was found between stocking operations and ecological improvements. The documented progress consistently stemmed from **targeted management actions** (hydromorphological restoration, pollution control, etc.), thereby highlighting the *inherent limitations* of stocking as a conservation tool.

17.4. WHY CONSERVATION STOCKING IS NOT WORKING

The past 50 years of numerous unsuccessful stocking programs, coupled with the very low number of true successes attributable to stocking, raise the question of why these programs are ineffective. This is especially true for conservation stocking, as well as reintroduction and mitigation programs. Enhancement stocking programs are inherently different and can be more easily successful, since the “wildness” of hatchery-reared fish, as well as wild salmon in rivers, is not the primary target.

The ineffectiveness of stocking programs for Atlantic salmon is a global phenomenon (Brown and Day 2002, Hutchings 2014, Lennox et al. 2021, McMillan et al. 2023, NASCO 2024), which is not unique to this species (Cochran-Biederman et al. 2015). The appropriateness and potential benefits of stocking, when weighed against its risks, are strongly questioned and challenged by scientists (Aas et al. 2018, Brown and Day 2002, Harrison and Berseth 2024, Hutchings 2014, Lennox et al. 2021, McMillan et al. 2023) and international conservation organizations (NASCO 2017; 2024).

// 7.4.1 LACK OF ASSIMILATION OF THE AVAILABLE SCIENTIFIC KNOWLEDGE

One difficulty is that most stocking programs are not scientifically driven, and the monitoring of these programs is also not scientifically defined, except for some programs such as those published by Bacon et al. (2015) and Glover et al. (2018). This lack of scientific rigor may lead to incomplete results for some programs, while, due to local adaptation and the highly diverse stocking practices, intermediate results may vary. Overall, as seen in studies of comparative biology and the effects *in natura* of stocking hatchery-reared salmon, scientific knowledge is robust and available. Results and knowledge about comparative biology and effects *in natura* explain the reasons why stocking programs fail. Failing to account for this available knowledge before initiating a program may lead to poorly defined aims and methods, while neglecting scientific knowledge during implementation hinders adaptive management of stocking programs — an approach actively pursued in other countries by stakeholders including anglers (Trushenski et al. 2015).

The issue of unassimilated scientific knowledge is particularly acute in France. Unlike other countries where scientific knowledge is effectively transferred to and utilized by decision-makers involved in restocking schemes, French stocking practices have shown minimal evolution (Aas et al. 2018). While scientific limitations of stocking are well documented, failure to address them may lead to unintended consequences (Trushenski et al. 2015) and wasteful expenditure of effort, time, and resources (Horreo et al. 2012, Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013). Although scientific knowledge often provides testable solutions, their implementation is frequently obstructed by socio-political-economic factors (Thorstad et al. 2021). Furthermore, population-specific knowledge gaps persist regarding local adaptation, particularly in demography, genetics, and region-specific threats (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009). But behavioral knowledge are also important. For example, in the Penobscot River, understanding homing behavior proved critical to understand the results of the restoration program (Gorsky et al. 2009). In another example, Hagelin et al. (2016) radio-tagged wild and hatchery-reared salmon to track them and better understand how they move in the river.

// 7.4.2 LACK OF ACTION IN ADDRESSING DRIVERS OF DECLINE AND THREATS

As reviewed previously, successful stocking programs have targeted numerous habitat restoration measures. Without complementary actions, a stocking program is likely to fail. Scientific studies have consistently noted this point: stocking is unlikely to be successful in the absence of concurrent habitat rehabilitation and harvest management strategies (Bacon et al. 2015, Cochran-Biederman et al. 2015, Lennox et al. 2021, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Molony et al. 2003, NASCO 2024, Prignon et al. 1999, Trushenski et al. 2015, Van Puijebroek et al. 2019, Van Rijssel et al. 2024). Indeed, the major threats to Atlantic salmon populations must be identified and addressed locally before considering conservation stocking. As noted by Trushenski et al. (2015), stocking of hatchery-reared salmon is often seen as a “quick fix”, but like other quick fixes, it is unlikely to resolve systemic issues unless applied as part of a comprehensive solution. In that way, stocking has been used to help dealing populations impacted by dams, pollution, or exploitation without addressing those threats (Lennox et al. 2021, Malange 2011, McMillan et al. 2023). For instance, one major threat to salmon is the increasing mortality at sea, which is exacerbated by climate change and the Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated (IUU) exploitation of marine resources (Dadswell et al. 2022). Stocking a population where the primary threat is high marine mortality will not support recovery and may even increase competition at the juvenile stage, potentially with maladapted individuals (Dadswell et al. 2022, Jonsson and Jonsson 2006).

Viable populations of Atlantic salmon are found mainly in rivers that are at least 85% accessible, while rivers where populations are extinct or where stocking operations have been implemented have an average accessibility of only 25% (Van Puijebroek et al. 2019). This result illustrates that stocking is often used as a quick fix, without addressing the main local threats to the population. In this context, and particularly regarding habitat connectivity, the stocking programs in the river *Meuse* (France) and the river *Testebo* (Sweden) provide instructive examples (similar results have already been reviewed for the Rhine, Garonne, Dordogne, and Bidasoa rivers). In the Meuse, the mortality rate of hatchery-reared smolts was relatively low in the free-flowing section, but mortality was high in the estuary and dammed sections (up to 90% in the estuary and 45% in the dammed river), mainly because smolts used hydroelectric power plants rather than fishways to pass dams and faced increased predation near dams (Brevé et al. 2013). Only 2--3% of smolts escaped into the North Sea (Brevé et al. 2013).

In the river Testebo, monitoring of the out-migration of hatchery-reared smolts indicated that 48--69% of smolts died in the river, and 43--47% in the estuary. The authors argued that hatchery-based recovery of this wild salmon population will not be successful unless other actions, such as habitat improvement, are included (Serrano et al. 2009). Moreover, Atlantic salmon is a species that demonstrates strong compensatory growth and survival; thus, stocking may be inefficient or even detrimental depending on density-dependent processes. Habitat restoration — either of breeding or growth habitats for fry — may be a more effective strategy for improving population abundance (Einum et al. 2008).

// 7.4.3 LACK OF EVALUATION AND INADEQUATE EVALUATION

A critical gap in stocking programs lies in evaluation. Without proper evaluation, adaptive management becomes impossible. Furthermore, since most stocking operations lack clearly defined aims and objectives, their suitability cannot be adequately assessed. For conservation stocking programs,

metrics such as rapid increases in population abundance and productivity, as well as diversity in a broad sense (genetics, behavioral, phenotypic, phenological, and life history traits), must be evaluated to maintain and improve population viability. These elements, however, are often negatively impacted by stocking, as previously reviewed. Despite this, none of the programs analyzed — and even fewer targeting specific conservation issues — conduct comprehensive assessments, leading to likely adverse effects on population diversity. Such impacts can be deleterious and may have long-term consequences for populations (O'Sullivan et al. 2020). Despite the multi-decadal duration of many programs, long-term effects are rarely examined, except in studies assessing genetic diversity (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Finnegan and Stevens 2008, O'Sullivan et al. 2020, Thorstad et al. 2021, Waples et al. 2007).

To conduct meaningful evaluations and determine whether a stocking program is necessary or well-designed, it is essential to establish the population's baseline state (abundance, demography, life history, diversity) prior to stocking, as outlined in the “Demographic and Modeling Evaluation” section (Lennox et al. 2021). Defining this initial state is mandatory for implementing Before-After-Control-Impact (BACI) evaluations, such as in the experimental study by Radinger et al. (2023). Using a BACI design, the authors compared stocking to habitat restoration and found that ecosystem-based habitat management was more effective at enhancing fish populations, while stocking produced no changes in abundance. Although this study focused on non-salmonids in a lake, it exemplifies the potential for applying BACI approaches to fish conservation programs.

Parallel to the lack of BACI evaluation, the absence of adaptive management is reflected in the scarcity of periodic program assessments. It is regrettable that no conservation stocking program conducts annual evaluations to enable adaptive adjustments.

Additionally, stocking programs should not prioritize maintaining hatcheries; the core strategy of salmon restoration must focus on maximizing the number of wild smolts escaping to the sea under optimal conditions (Thorstad et al. 2021). This emphasis is critical because most demographic evaluations rely solely on adult returns. Juvenile production and smolt escapement should also be monitored — a step rarely taken. Overall, evaluations are typically inadequate in both temporal scope (e.g., seasonal assessments, pre-/post-intervention comparisons) and metrics examined (e.g., abundance, demography, life history, genetics/behavioral/phenotypic diversity).

// 7.4.4 LACK OF ADAPATIVE HATCHERY PRODUCTION

For most stocking programs, including those for conservation, the production of salmon to be stocked takes place in hatcheries, sometimes private ones. The production methods and zoo-technical considerations are generally quite similar across programs, with the main difference being whether the hatchery is local or not. Aside from this, grow-out ponds and egg development facilities are largely comparable. After development, the release stage varies among programs, with the choice of release stage usually driven by production costs and local historical practices. In practice, new or alternative methods to improve the quality of stocked salmon (i.e., their similarity to wild individuals), reduce the impact *in natura*, or enhance the efficiency of stocking operations are rarely tested. This is largely because most programs are not scientifically driven and lack adaptive management, as mentioned above.

Some trials have been conducted, and results are available to improve the production of “wild-

type” hatchery-reared salmon and increase the efficiency of stocking. For instance, some programs have attempted to produce juveniles not in hatcheries but in nursery creeks (Dumas 1981, Naish et al. 2007, Prouzet and Gaignon 1981, Richard 1987). These results can serve as recommendations and are reviewed in the next section. However, a persistent issue in hatchery production is the reduced genetic diversity observed in the offspring (see Section 6.1.1, page 64, and Section 5.2.4, page 58). Due to domestication selection, even if the adults used as broodstock adequately represent the genetic diversity of the population, losses of genetic variability can occur in juveniles if the crosses between adults are not well designed — for example, if the eggs of one female are fertilized by the sperm of only one or two males (Machado-Schiaffino et al. 2007). Sometimes, local wild individuals cannot be caught, or there are not enough available, so part or all of the broodstock comes from another population. In such cases, the genetic divergence between the local population and the source population, arising from local adaptation, may explain the failure of stocking operations (Gabián et al. 2022).

// 7.4.5 LACK IN BROODSTOCK SOURCE AND MANAGEMENT

Atlantic salmon exhibit strong local adaptation (Côte et al. 2012; 2016, Hutchings 2014), which often results in poor outcomes when broodstock from non-local populations are used—a common cause of failure in fish stocking programs (Cochran-Biederman et al. 2015). Nevertheless, numerous stocking initiatives have historically relied on foreign or non-local adults (Almodóvar et al. 2020, Gabián et al. 2022, Gayou and Roguet 1996, Ingendhal and Beeck 2011, Schneider 2011, Van Rijssel et al. 2024). The use of such broodstock can lead to the introgression of maladapted alleles, as well as the erosion of genetic diversity and population structure (Gabián et al. 2022, Hagen et al. 2019, Perrier et al. 2014).

Another important issue concerns broodstock management, specifically the number of individuals used and whether all are replaced each year. For example, some programs maintain 20 broodstock individuals, with half being renewed annually (Milot et al. 2013). Retaining individuals in hatcheries across multiple spawning seasons may increase domestication selection (Christie et al. 2012, Horreo et al. 2008). Both the number of broodstock individuals and the crossing schemes employed typically reduce the genetic diversity of produced juveniles compared to that observed in wild populations (Fraser 2008, Horreo et al. 2008, Selly et al. 2014).

// 7.4.6 FISHERIES

In addition to the lack of habitat restoration measures, the relationship with fisheries is sometimes problematic. Firstly, stocking programs—including conservation initiatives — may lead to increased fishing pressure on the population if fisheries are not properly adjusted or regulated, resulting in detrimental effects (Bousquet 1996, Lorenzen et al. 2012, NASCO 2024).

Another issue is that the perceptions and attitudes of fishermen towards conservation plans can be misguided if they are not clearly involved in the process or if the aims and results are not communicated effectively (Arlinghaus and Mehner 2005, Bryan 1977, Perry et al. 2024). Moreover, failing to involve anglers in conservation programs can sometimes be counterproductive (Thorstad et al. 2021). Like other citizens, policies and decisions that disconnect users such as anglers, or cause them to feel alienated from conservation efforts, may undermine long-term conservation objectives, since public

engagement is a critical element in efforts to conserve, restore, and enhance Atlantic salmon populations (Thorstad et al. 2021).

Overall, whether professional fishermen, anglers, or other users of wild rivers, insufficient involvement in the monitoring and communication of conservation efforts remains a significant issue (Harrison and Berseth 2024).

// 7.4.7 TIME-SCALE

Most stocking programs are perpetuated over several decades, whereas stocking operations implemented as short-term interventions to prevent imminent extinction are considered more likely to achieve long-term population viability than approaches requiring prolonged supplementation, which perpetuate the fitness costs associated with hatchery rearing (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Stocking programs may also reduce natural recruitment through density-dependent processes, thereby increasing dependence on continued captive breeding unless available habitat is expanded. As previously mentioned, the time scale typically used to define stocking programs is often inappropriate, as programs tend to last too long, whereas conservation stocking should only be established for a limited number of years (Griffiths et al. 2011, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Ritter 1997, Wolter 2015).

Another issue related to time scale, aside from evaluation, is the mismatch between funding cycles and the duration of effective programs. Funding cycles are usually between one and three years, which is insufficient for a stocking program designed to last five years, especially when considering the need for several years of monitoring before and after for BACI evaluation.

In summary

Below a summary of the reasons for the lack of success in previous attempts at stocking programs (Molony et al. 2003, Trushenski et al. 2015, adapted from):

- Lack of understanding of the complex ecology of the ecosystem into which reared animals are stocked
- Lack of understanding of the biology and ecology of the population to be stocked
- The stocking program did not attempt to identify or control the causes of decline in the wild stock
- The stocking program had poorly defined objectives
- The stocking program had no planned evaluation
- Impacts of the stocking program on wild stocks and the ecosystem were not considered or investigated
- The stocking program was used in isolation from other management tools

- Lack of stakeholder involvement in the planning and execution of the stocking program from the outset
- The stocking program lacked a scientific approach and did not incorporate a pilot trial
- Ignoring the need to establish a structured decision-making process
- Failure to thoroughly integrate flexible and adaptive management into the stocking program
- The stocking program could not be evaluated because released animals were not identifiable
- The stocking program could not be evaluated because no prior state was available
- The stocking program was not evaluated over a sufficient time frame (evaluation ceased prior to recruitment of the released animals into a fishery)
- The stocking program was not evaluated for effects on demography and diversity (genetic, behavioral, phenotypic, phenological, and life history traits)
- The stocking program did not account for the differences between hatchery-reared and wild salmon
- The stocking program did not attempt to test new or alternative salmon production methods beyond conventional hatchery practices
- The stocking program included no analysis of costs and/or cost-benefits
- No clearly defined endpoint for the stocking program
- Lack of clear fishery-management perspectives

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PART IV

Perspectives and recommendations

CHAPTER 8

Criteria, timing, definition & governance for initiating salmon stocking program

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The perspectives and recommendations reviewed and discussed here are **drawn directly from proposals by authors in the scientific literature**. While some of these approaches may have already been tested in certain programs, their effectiveness can vary significantly depending on local adaptation and specific contextual factors. Therefore, it is essential for stakeholders to carefully consider each recommendation in light of their unique circumstances — and, where possible, to evaluate or test these elements within their own context before implementation.

18.1. CRITERIA FOR CONSIDERING OR AVOIDING STOCKING HATCHERY-REARED FISH

This document focuses on **conservation stocking**, with recommendations reviewed within this context. The primary action stakeholders should consider when contemplating stocking programs is to protect remaining wild salmon populations (Lennox et al. 2021).

A critical first step in deciding whether to implement stocking involves gathering comprehensive data on the local environment and population characteristics, including abundance, demography, genetic diversity, phenotypic diversity, and threats (Cochran-Biederman et al. 2015, Molony et al. 2003). This baseline assessment should:

- Establish historical abundance trends (Molony et al. 2003)
- Identify Biological Reference Points (Lennox et al. 2021, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Malcolm et al. 2019, NASCO 2024)
- Estimate carrying capacity to avoid overstocking (Koed et al. 2020, Lorenzen et al. 2012)
- Document existing genetic diversity as an adaptation reservoir (Lennox et al. 2021, Thorstad et al. 2021)
- Analyze genetic structure and gene flow among proximate populations (Perrier et al. 2014)
- Identify population bottlenecks and viability threats (Brevé et al. 2013, Koed et al. 2020)

This knowledge is essential for understanding current population status, demographic trends, ecosystem function, conservation priorities, and recovery strategies.

Effective recovery requires addressing key threats including (Koed et al. 2020, Lennox et al. 2021, NASCO 2024): habitat degradation and fragmentation, pollution, predation pressure, fishing impacts (commercial, recreational, illegal). Threat mitigation through habitat restoration (e.g., dam removal, water quality improvements) often enables natural recolonization (Ikediashi et al. 2012, Perrier et al. 2010, Saavedra-Nieves et al. 2020). Ecosystem-based management should precede and accompany any stocking initiative (Einum et al. 2008, Holden et al. 2024, NASCO 2024, Radinger et al. 2023). Stocking programs designed to compensate for anthropogenic impacts (e.g., dam construction) should generally be avoided, as they often fail ecologically while perpetuating the misconception that environmental damage can be offset (McMillan et al. 2023, Trushenski et al. 2015).

Stocking should only be considered as a last resort, specifically for facilitating recolonization following substantial habitat restoration programs or for mitigating severe demographic bottlenecks while maintaining adequate genetic diversity—either through demographic rescue or genetic rescue (Carlson et al. 2014, Fraser 2008, Johnsen et al. 2014, Koed et al. 2020, McMillan et al. 2023, Thorstad et al. 2021). Genetic rescue may be possible when an existing gene bank is available for the population, and stocking can be used to increase genetic diversity (Johnsen et al. 2014, Lennox et al. 2021). However, even historical gene banks may contain maladapted alleles if local ecosystems have changed (Johnsen et al. 2014, Lennox et al. 2021). An alternative approach is the translocation of a limited number of individuals from a comparable population (Pregler et al. 2023), although this strategy must be tested for the species in question. Regarding demographic rescue, modeling can help determine its potential effectiveness. For instance, a recent study investigated how stocking may serve as a rescue strategy for species experiencing Allee effects, such as those considered here (Kanarek et al. 2015). The authors found that such interventions are only likely to succeed if favorable ecological conditions are present or if the population undergoes rapid adaptive evolution.

Finally, natural recolonization potential is frequently underestimated — salmon have demonstrated rapid upstream colonization within weeks of barrier removal in French rivers like the Nivelles and Sélune (Lasne et al. 2025). When proximate populations exist, priority should be given to habitat connectivity restoration over stocking to encourage natural straying (Ikediashi et al. 2012, Perrier et al. 2010, Saavedra-Nieves et al. 2020). Finally, small populations often remain viable due to high fecundity and compensatory dynamics in salmon. So knowing historical population abundance and fluctuations is necessary and in most cases, performing stocking operations in such cases would be more harmful than beneficial in such cases (Bacon et al. 2015, Dauphin et al. 2017, Jonsson and Jonsson 2006, Laffaille 2011, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Wallace and Curry 2017).

I 8.2. STEPS TO DEFINE AN APPROPRIATE SALMON STOCKING PROGRAM

Conservation stocking should be implemented alongside multiple other management measures and should be limited to a short time frame (typically several years; Griffiths et al. 2011, Lorenzen

et al. 2012, Ritter 1997, Wolter 2015). Indeed, although a purely demographic rescue relying solely on stocking may require 15-20 years to **potentially** re-establish a viable population (Fraser 2008), the long-term impacts on genetic diversity and overall population viability can be substantial (Bowlby and Gibson 2011, Hagen et al. 2021, Naish et al. 2007). Prior to program implementation, it is crucial to acquire comprehensive data and knowledge, as the establishment of effective restoration goals is often hindered by insufficient understanding of the population (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009).

The ultimate goals and objectives of any stocking program should be clearly defined and articulated before the program begins to ensure proper evaluation and adaptive management (Fraser 2008, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Lorenzen et al. 2012, NASCO 2024). Both the program's objectives and the stocking strategy itself must be scientifically defensible (Fraser 2008). Prior to defining the program, and to facilitate its evaluation, modeling should be used to test management scenarios and predict their impacts on the population (Legault 2005).

A comprehensive management plan should specify when stocking is appropriate and include explicit, scientifically grounded goals and objectives for the target population (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009, Trushenski et al. 2015). Based on these objectives and the scientific knowledge gathered prior to the stocking program, a robust planning and evaluation framework should be established, allowing assessment against the *a priori* defined objectives (Molony et al. 2003, Trushenski et al. 2015). Furthermore, the program and its stakeholders must be capable of adapting to new information and results as they emerge through scientific monitoring (Fraser 2008).

Clear endpoints for the stocking program should be established before its initiation (Fraser 2008, Harrison and Berseth 2024), and the adaptive management plan should allow for early termination of the program if the stocking of hatchery-reared individuals results in significant negative effects on the population (Molony et al. 2003).

18.3. GOVERNANCE AND SOCIAL ASPECTS IN PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION

People tend to support and conserve what they know. Thorstad et al. (2021) emphasized that the social, cultural, and economic values of salmon, as well as the communities connected to them, are essential for maintaining public, political, and financial support for conservation programs. An effective and sustainable restoration program must take into account the social context in which it operates (Harrison and Berseth 2024), as well as relevant legal and political perspectives (Trushenski et al. 2015). Program evaluation should include an assessment of social aspects, particularly the degree of public involvement and support (Harrison and Berseth 2024, Thorstad et al. 2021, Trushenski et al. 2015). Prior to implementing any program, it is crucial to conduct outreach and communication efforts to inform and engage the public (Kochalski et al. 2019). However, public engagement alone should not be used as a justification for stocking, as there are numerous alternative actions — such as habitat restoration or science education — that can achieve similar goals without relying on hatchery interventions.

Another key consideration in stocking programs is the organization and coordination among the various stakeholders involved. Flye et al. (2021) demonstrated that the structure of the partnership network is a significant determinant of program efficiency, particularly regarding adaptive management. Involving a diverse array of socio-economic actors in restoration efforts increases the likelihood of positive outcomes. Social-ecological management approaches, structured around shared values and a comprehensive understanding of the system, are more likely to succeed (Cote et al. 2021). It is therefore important to integrate both national and local actors within the program framework. For example, the Atlantic Salmon Recovery Framework (ASRF) is organized into three levels: a policy board, a management board, and action teams comprising various local partners (Flye et al. 2021). The Policy Board sets policy direction, reaffirms priorities annually, and allocates necessary resources, while the Management Board establishes recovery priorities, develops decision-making frameworks, provides direction, and ensures transparency in resource allocation (Flye et al. 2021). However, it is important to keep in mind that scientists provide recommendations and enable objective evaluation and results, which serve as information to guide decisions made by stakeholders (Mann and Plummer 2000).

Nevertheless, highly diversified actor networks can sometimes result in slow and ineffective decision-making, unclear leadership and accountability, and reduced adaptive capacity (Flye et al. 2021). For instance, in France, decentralized decision-making authority and non-centralized program governance and data management — compared to other countries — have hindered effective management and scientific knowledge transfer in stocking programs, not only for salmonids (Aas et al. 2018). Therefore, it is essential to clearly define the roles and relationships of all actors, establish a clear hierarchy (i.e., decision-making authority), and ensure effective communication channels. Such organization, and periodic reorganization, can enable collaborative governance that combines national and local actors, fosters long-term inter-organizational relationships, and optimizes communication pathways (Flye et al. 2021).

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CHAPTER 9

Technical aspects of stocking: from fish rearing to post-release assessment

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9.1. PRODUCTION OF HATCHERY-REARED FISH

We already saw that hatchery-reared fish differ in numerous points to their wild counterparts and that stocking hatchery-reared fish may usually lead to negative effects on wild populations. In order to improve stocking programs by reducing negative effects in the wild populations and improving stocking efficiency, numerous studies have tested different methods and recommended some practical points, while some reviews are available on these questions, mostly related to hatchery conditions (Brown and Day 2002, Näslund 2021). However, numerous other practical considerations can be questioned, tested, and improved. As said by Lorenzen et al. (2012), developmental manipulations (e.g., temperature-water currents, nutrition, feeding practices) to promote wild traits are important to raise performance after release, and some such manipulations may also reduce selection for culture traits. In that way, environmental enrichment, life-skills training and soft release strategies can successfully promote behavioural skills that may increase survival (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Exposure to variable spatial and foraging cues in the hatchery environment provides fish with enhanced behavioural traits that may be associated with improved survival in the wild (Lorenzen et al. 2012).

// 9.1.1 BROODSTOCK AND CROSSING

The main questions regarding broodstock management are which salmon to capture, how many individuals are needed, and how to handle them. The first recommendation is to use local wild salmon to ensure that individuals are adapted to the local environment (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Indeed, the strong local adaptation observed in salmon (Côte et al. 2012; 2016, Hutchings 2014) means that hatchery-reared fish derived from local adults generally perform better on most criteria than those originating from foreign populations (Lorenzen et al. 2012).

The next recommendation concerns the number of individuals to capture, aiming to preserve as much wild genetic diversity as possible (Fraser 2008, Horreo et al. 2008, Selly et al. 2014). The greater

the number of broodstock individuals, the higher the genetic diversity that can be maintained. For example, Witzemberger and Hochkirch (2011) found a positive correlation between captive population size and the number of founders, showing that maintaining a captive population larger than 15 individuals often allows retention of approximately 90% of the expected heterozygosity (H_e) in the juveniles produced. Although this is a general guideline not specific to salmon, Milot et al. (2013) maintained a broodstock of 20 individuals - a number that can be challenging to achieve in small populations, which are typically the focus of conservation stocking. Another important recommendation is to avoid keeping adults in the hatchery for multiple breeding seasons, as prolonged retention may increase domestication selection (Christie et al. 2012, Milot et al. 2013).

In addition to the number of broodstock individuals, their relative parental contributions are critical (Bacon et al. 2015, Lorenzen et al. 2012, Selly et al. 2014). The best practice combines a factorial mating design, which maximizes the genetic diversity of offspring, with equalization of family size to minimize inadvertent selection (Lorenzen et al. 2012). Although such practices can be challenging to implement, one program demonstrated feasibility by dividing the ova from each female into 10 batches, each fertilized by a different male, including precocious male parr (Bacon et al. 2015). Males were rotated among females to maximize the number of sires contributing to the juveniles (Bacon et al. 2015). After fertilization, the 10 batches from each female were recombined into a single batch. Including precocious male parr is particularly important for populations where a high proportion of juveniles are sired by these males, so it is necessary to have this information from the wild population.

Finally, it is essential to monitor which individuals constitute the broodstock, how crosses are performed, and the parentage of all juveniles produced. Many stocking program assessments remain incomplete due to missing critical demographic data (e.g., size, number of founders), genetic information (e.g., effective population size, inbreeding coefficient), or breeding details (e.g., number and genetic characteristics of breeders, pedigree, mating schemes). In that line, the stocking program in the Bidaosa offers the perfect example to show that such a monitoring is possible. These data are necessary for proper monitoring and evaluation of stocking programs and their effects in the wild (Fraser 2008, Ritter 1997, Witzemberger and Hochkirch 2011).

// 9.1.2 HATCHERY CONDITIONS AND ENRICHMENT

The main question related to improving hatchery conditions and enrichment is how to rear more wild-like hatchery salmon (Näslund 2021). In this context, Näslund (2021) reviewed the available knowledge on hatchery conditions and linked it to the ability of fish to “learn”. The central idea is to enrich hatchery environments and improve conditions to promote the expression of more wild-like behavior in hatchery-reared fish (Näslund 2021). This concept is not new, as Brown and Day (2002) already discussed life-skills training aimed at enhancing wild-like behaviors in hatchery-reared fish.

In hatchery production, numerous methods have been tested to improve wild-like behaviors, including tank enrichment with artificial plants (Brockmark et al. 2007, Mes et al. 2019, Prentice et al. 2025), increasing water flow rates to better mimic natural conditions (Hatanpää et al. 2020, Jonsson and Jonsson 2009), providing shelters (Hatanpää et al. 2020, Hyvärinen and Rodewald 2013, Jonsson

et al. 2014, Mes et al. 2019, Molony et al. 2003, Solås et al. 2019), adding rocks (Brockmark et al. 2007, Hyvärinen and Rodewald 2013, Mes et al. 2019), and reducing stocking densities (Brockmark et al. 2007, Johnsson et al. 2014, Liu et al. 2015, Molony et al. 2003).

Hatcheries should ideally be supplied with water from the targeted population to ensure proper water imprinting. Additionally, water temperature should match natural conditions *in natura* (Jonsson et al. 2019). Water velocity (Jonsson and Jonsson 2009), and environmental variability, should be as found in nature, in order to benefit fish development by producing individuals with more wild-like behavior and neural development (Hatanpää et al. 2020, Johnsson et al. 2014).

Regarding enrichment, Prentice et al. (2025) found that the presence of artificial plants led to bolder parr and more cohesive social behavior. Mes et al. (2019) tested artificial plants combined with shelters; despite no observed differences in neurobiological characteristics compared to standard hatchery conditions, individuals from enriched environments (plants + shelters rearranged weekly to ensure environmental variability) exhibited 51% higher survival, demonstrating the importance of such enrichments (Mes et al. 2019). Tank enrichment with rocks, shelters, and painted tank bottoms featuring false rocks from early stages until smoltification resulted in smolts displaying higher migration speeds and survival compared to those from standard tanks (Hyvärinen and Rodewald 2013). However, in another study, salmon reared under conventional or enriched hatchery conditions and released as fry showed no consistent reduction in immediate predation mortality (2 days post-release) and no improvement—or even negative effects—on recapture rates 2–3 months after release (Solås et al. 2019). The authors also observed that tank enrichment tended to reduce growth (Solås et al. 2019). They hypothesized that the effects of shelters may vary depending on the life stage at which they are applied, and that enrichment alone cannot reduce post-release mortality.

Indeed, responses to enrichment may differ depending on the broodstock population and its specific characteristics. For example, Brockmark et al. (2007) found no effect of enrichment (rocks and artificial plants) on post-release survival. They also tested density effects ($3.75 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ vs. $1.355 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) without observing survival differences. Regarding density, Liu et al. (2015) found that low stocking density increased growth and reduced cortisol levels without affecting hatchery mortality (post-release mortality was not assessed). Their low density ranged from 7.57 to $15.71 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$, compared to 30.18 to $61.34 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ for high density (Liu et al. 2015). These density values are much higher than those tested by Brockmark et al. (2007) or Rosengren et al. (2017). Rosengren et al. (2017) also tested density effects alongside shelter presence, finding that low density ($50 \text{ ind}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ vs. $150 \text{ ind}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) increased growth and migration success, whereas shelters reduced migration success (Rosengren et al. 2017).

Improved post-release survival was also reported by Harbicht et al. (2020) when comparing standard practices to improved methods involving more natural water temperatures and release timing adjusted to fish development. In this study, juveniles exhibiting more natural growth rates—similar to the slowest-growing hatchery individuals—were released (Harbicht et al. 2020). These results support adjusting hatchery conditions and releasing fish with developmental rates similar to wild individuals in the target population. Environmental enrichment may slow growth compared to standard hatchery conditions, thereby producing more natural growth patterns, as observed by Delaval et al. (2021).

Whether tested individually or in combination (Hatanpää et al. 2020), these hatchery environment adjustments must be tailored to each case, as individual responses depend on the phenotypic plasticity and genetic diversity specific to each population (Hatanpää et al. 2020). Moreover, although “shelters” and “density” have been studied, the shelter types, density levels, and life stages at which effects were assessed vary among studies. For example, the shelters used by Rosengren et al. (2017) consisted of submerged shredded black polyethylene material covering approximately half the tank area and volume. The shreds were bundled for easy removal and cleaning, with each bundle containing 100 shreds (50 cm × 7 cm) threaded on a 150 cm long polyester rope. In contrast, Hyvärinen and Rodewald (2013) defined shelters as three sheets of 2 mm × 500 mm × 250 mm polystyrene supported by metal legs.

// 9.1.3 DEVELOPMENTAL STAGE RELEASED

One key aspect of stocking programs is the developmental stage at which hatchery fish are released. Some programs stock fish at a single stage, while others release multiple stages or change the release stage over time.

In two rivers in Denmark, Birnie-Gauvin et al. (2018) compared the release of the upper modal group of half-year-olds in the fall with the lower modal group of one-year-olds in early summer. Fish stocked in the fall as half-year-olds (upper modal group) exhibited the highest emigration rate and emigrated later than other stocked fish. Consequently, the authors recommend stocking the upper modal group of half-year-olds because they have a greater probability of migration (potentially due to age at release, higher growth rate, or shorter freshwater residence) and are cheaper to produce due to less time spent in the hatchery (Birnie-Gauvin et al. 2018). However, the release stage interacts with release timing. For instance, stocking large parr in late autumn may conflict with the natural timing of smolt migration, as stocked individuals may not be ready to migrate, thereby delaying their migration (Skilbrei et al. 2010). The timing of release, in terms of season, may also affect the success of stocking. For example, Karppinen et al. (2014) found that smolts released early in the spring into cold waters ceased migration after a brief downstream movement and were vulnerable to predation, whereas smolts released later in the spring exhibited markedly increased migration speed and survival rates.

Depending on the program, Zydlewski et al. (2014) also recommends targeting lower-mode fish. Lower-mode fish—those not growing fast enough to smolt by the time of stocking—are a by-product of smolt programs and represent an intermediate hatchery product. For example, in the river Maine stocking program, stakeholders produce both fry and smolts in hatcheries. Lower-mode fish, which produce age-1 and age-2 smolts, exhibited higher survival than hatchery smolts (likely due to less domestication) and can be targeted as a true stocking life stage since these individuals have greater freshwater experience and may possess growth and fitness advantages. However, in a Finnish experiment, Salminen et al. (2007) found higher recapture rates for individuals stocked as 2-year-old summer smolts compared to 1-year-old summer smolts and parr. This program focused on fisheries enhancement, so migrating adults may not necessarily participate in reproduction. In such cases, the “quality” of adults in terms of wild-like behavior and domestication is less critical than it would be in a conservation program.

Overall, early life stages have the potential to be more successful. For example, Jokikokko et al.

(2006) found higher survival and recapture rates for salmon stocked as 1-year-old parr compared to 2-year-old smolts. Similarly, Hagen et al. (2021) concluded that parr have greater potential for success than smolt releases. In an extensive study, hatchery fry released into the wild were compared to individuals retained in the hatchery for 22 and 55 days (Stringwell et al. 2014). Survivors exhibited longer heads, thicker caudal peduncles, and more streamlined body shapes than hatchery controls, reflecting phenotypic plasticity and non-random selective mortality of maladapted phenotypes (Stringwell et al. 2014). Streamlined body shapes and longer heads are adaptations to fast water currents (Stringwell et al. 2014). Thus, plasticity in early life stages supports stocking fish at early stages, which also ensures greater freshwater experience. Additionally, smaller stocked salmon had higher survival rates than larger salmon when predation by birds was investigated (Miyamoto et al. 2018).

// 9.1.4 RELEASING

Hatchery-reared salmon have to be released; the question is how and where. But the first element to question to improve a program is on the transport of individuals since it has a cost which is higher for smolts than for fry (Salminen et al. 2007) and transport increase cortisol concentrations (Roberts et al. 2024).

Some programs target stocking locations than are not in zones where natural reproduction occurs (i.e., refuge zone). However, one element to account is that fry may disperse upstream with median dispersal distances of 400 m (Eisenhauer et al. 2021). In addition, it is maybe better to stock individuals in more upstream sites and in tributaries than downstream, since individuals stocked near tributaries migrate upstream faster (Gorsky et al. 2009). However, stocking sites depend also to the stocking stage since smolts released at river mouth exhibited a higher survivorship (30%) than smolts released in the river (12%) probably due to predation and the lower adapted migration behavior of hatchery-reared fish (Thorstad et al. 2012). Those results also depends on the targeted rivers, notably whether numerous dams are present or not.

Another point is how fish are released. A study investigated whether it is better to release fish either grouped or dispersed. Authors found no differences in growth, dispersal and survival but the reach where the experiment was performed was only 1000-m long (Brunsdon et al. 2017), which is only twice the median dispersal distances found by (Eisenhauer et al. 2021). So, this question has to be addresses in rivers. A study also investigated wether a soft-releasing tactic with the use of enclosures in-situ during six days before the releasing may improve the success of stocking. The soft-releasing tactic diminished the upstream dispersal, which can be a good point, and lead to an earlier downstream migration (Mokdad et al. 2022). A soft-releasing tactic may also reduce glucose and lactate concentrations (Roberts et al. 2024) that are secondary physiological stress indicators. Another possibility is the use of automatic release cages as Glover and Stephen (2023).

Finally, several studies found stocking and releasing at night increase survival in river (Glover and Stephen 2023, Vollset et al. 2017), favor migratory behavior during night as wild-fish (Roberts et al. 2009), and increase survival in early marine migration (Vollset et al. 2017).

// 9.1.5 ALTERNATIVES TO HATCHERY

One solution to improve stocking practices and the efficiency of stocking programs is to use alternatives to conventional hatcheries. This question is not new; for example, Beall and Marty (1983), Dumas et al. (1979), Prouzet and Gagnon (1981), Richard (1987) tested production in nursery creeks, Arrignon (1973) used floating incubators directly in the river, and Dumas (1981) tested production in a pond. While evaluation methods of stocking programs have evolved considerably since these studies, they provide good examples demonstrating that alternative production methods are feasible and where already suggested as potential tools to replace traditional hatchery production in stocking program (Beall and Marty 1983). Moreover, choosing such production methods can lead to more wild-like stocked fish, as individuals are reared in natural conditions and, in the case of floating incubators and nursery creeks, directly within the targeted system. Additionally, these methods—especially nursery creeks—offer much lower economic costs per produced juvenile. More recent reviews recommend the use of semi-natural ponds, stream-side incubation, and the incorporation of substrata in incubation facilities (Ritter 1997).

In the absence of production in nursery creeks or in-river incubators, some semi-alternative methods can be tested. Bamberger (2009) evaluated four alternatives to conventional hatcheries, including three semi-natural larger incubation systems, conventional hatchery troughs, and a Bamberger-box (see Bamberger 2009, Figure 1) used to incubate fry from the late-eyed stage onwards. A common feature of these four systems is the use of incubation gravel, although water supply and current vary among them. The authors found that all semi-natural incubation systems produced significantly longer and heavier fry than conventional hatchery troughs (Bamberger 2009) and demonstrated that semi-natural incubation systems can achieve high survival rates of Atlantic salmon fry (Bamberger 2009). More interestingly, temporal emigration patterns from Bamberger-boxes closely resembled natural emergence patterns on both seasonal and diurnal timescales. They also noted that the cost of producing a fish in semi-natural incubation systems is comparable to that of conventional methods (Bamberger 2009). An additional benefit is that fish may self-release into the river. However, these modifications to conventional hatchery troughs lead to higher costs for cleaning and maintaining the incubation medium.

I 9.2. EVALUATION AND MONITORING

Some studies have investigated evaluation and monitoring methods and provided direct recommendations or examples of “good practices”. These recommendations should be added to those already noted in the evaluation methods reviewed in Section 7.1, page 75. Overall, all monitoring and data acquisition that enable scientific planning and evaluation of a stocking program—based on the potential effects already reviewed—must be performed (Molony et al. 2003). Additionally, as previously mentioned, demographic modeling and *a priori* scenario testing can be suitable tools for evaluation. Some previous work may be used as food for thought: Bacon et al. (2015), Barton et al. (2020), Dauphin et al. (2017), Legault (2005). While models on population dynamics should be used, models that integrate several aspects like demo-genetic (Lamarins et al. 2022a;b) or life-cycle models (Beebe et al. 2021) should also be used to assess the relative importance of each threat before stocking, and the integrative impacts of stocking (Mann and Plummer 2000).

A first important element concerns the costs of stocking programs, since transport and rearing expenses can be significant but should be monitored to adopt best practices (Salminen et al. 2007). Monitoring these costs also enables cost-benefit analyses from an economic perspective (Kallio-Nyberg et al. 2013, Salminen et al. 2007), which should be incorporated into program evaluations (Molony et al. 2003). However, this is particularly relevant for enhancement programs where economic benefits are targeted, which should not be the case for conservation programs.

Given the importance of diversity (genetic, phenotypic, behavioral, etc.) in producing more wild-like hatchery-reared fish, monitoring broodstock composition, parental contribution, and maturity is necessary. Horreo et al. (2008) advocated for improved monitoring and control of these factors. In this context, Feuerstein et al. (2024) highlighted the importance of genetic variation as a primary metric in conservation genetics.

From a broader program perspective, many stocking programs have achieved measures of success in traditional fish production metrics associated with salmon hatcheries (e.g., high egg-to-smolt survival; adult-to-adult replacement rates exceeding 1.0). However, limited information is available regarding the performance of hatchery fish and, especially, their progeny in the natural environment (Waples et al. 2007). Therefore, stocking programs must improve monitoring and evaluation not only of adult returns but also of reproductive success and progeny survival. Authors have argued that evaluating stocking success requires a comprehensive assessment of potential benefits and risks, focusing on net long-term effects on wild populations (Waples et al. 2007). This emphasis on better monitoring of cost-benefits was also noted by García-Vega et al. (2025), who described stocking as a fishery management tool that particularly requires risk assessment and cost-effectiveness evaluation. They further proposed that a controlled cessation of stocking over several consecutive years could provide valuable insights into the population's capacity for natural sustainability.

PART V

Alosa-Specific Considerations & Concluding Remarks

ALLIS SHAD

Alosa alosa

CHAPTER

10

Alosa specificities

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10.1. CONTEXT

Research on the effects and implementation of stocking programs for *Alosa alosa* (Allis shad) and *Alosa fallax* (Twaite shad) is much less extensive and developed than for Atlantic salmon. For this reason, work on Atlantic salmon is used as a reference, to which we add the limited information available for shads. When no specific information on shads is available, we recommend basing all considerations on what is known for salmon, while highlighting the need to acquire the necessary knowledge for shad species. The principle that stocking should be used only as a last resort — after actions to improve habitat quality and connectivity — established for salmon, also applies to shads. Indeed, alongside climate change, shads are mainly impacted by habitat degradation, loss of connectivity, fishing pressure, and pollution (André et al. 2018, Limburg and Waldman 2009). These numerous threats also provide multiple opportunities for positive intervention.

Allis and Twaite shad populations have declined significantly across their native ranges due to habitat fragmentation (e.g., dam construction), overfishing, and degraded water quality (Aprahamian et al. 2003, Limburg and Waldman 2009, Maitland and Hatton-Ellis 2003, OSPAR 2021). For example, Allis shad in France have lost 69% of their historical distribution, with populations in the Loire and Garonne basins declining by over 95% since the 1990s (OSPAR 2021). Similarly, Twaite shad populations in the UK and Europe have contracted due to industrial pollution and migration barriers. Stocking programs have been implemented to supplement dwindling populations, restore genetic diversity, and aid recolonization of historical habitats (Hundt et al. 2015, Potoka and Smith 2023). While some straying occurs, which can reduce genetic structure among populations, shad exhibit strong homing

behavior that promotes substantial local adaptation (Martin et al. 2015, Randon et al. 2018). Another point, similar to salmon and likely explaining the limited success of most stocking programs, is that shad exhibit compensatory population dynamics (Martin 1996, McGrath et al. 2022).

10.2. STOCKING EVENTS AND PROGRAMS: WHAT CAN WE SAY?

In a review of stocking programs for shads, Hutchings (2014) listed only six programs, all focused on American shad (*Alosa sapidissima*). Among these six programs, three resulted in established or probably established populations (i.e., naturally reproducing populations), while three did not. This highlights the limited knowledge available on stocking programs for shad, even when considering American shad.

// 10.2.1 ALLIS SHAD

The **captive breeding** of allis shad has a long history; the Saint-Pierre-les-Elbeuf hatchery initiated production of allis shad and twait shad eggs as early as 1889 (Vincent 1894a). At that time, the author examined the **impact of the new Poses Dam on the Seine River** on shad spawning and discussed **stocking operations** in the Seine basin (Vincent 1894a;b).

One of the earliest attempts to stock Allis shad in France was related to fisheries enhancement in the river Loire in the 1920s (Le Clerc 1941). At that time, salmon populations in the Loire were already in sharp decline, whereas shad populations were not yet affected (Le Clerc 1941). This initiative followed earlier results from 1889 at Saint-Pierre-lès-Elbeuf on the lower Seine, where Pierre Vincent established a facility to apply American fish farming techniques developed by the Federal Fisheries Commission (Le Clerc 1941). While Vincent's experiment led to an increase in Twaite shad numbers from 7,490 in 1891 to 32,890 in 1894 at the start of his project, the experiment did not last (Le Clerc 1941). Subsequently, Le Clerc (1941) set up several incubator batteries for large numbers of shad eggs at a new research facility in Ponts-de-Cé on the Loire, 170 kilometers from the sea. For proper development, these eggs needed to be kept in suspension in the water, similar to pike and whitefish eggs. Attempts to maintain adults in tanks failed due to their extreme fragility, leading the authors to conclude that “it is impossible to keep shad in captivity” (Le Clerc 1941). Shad were captured at known spawning sites, but it was observed that females had sequential egg maturation (Le Clerc 1941). These findings, combined with the difficulty of keeping adults alive in captivity, led the authors to conclude that the best way to increase the number of wild individuals in the population would be to manage fisheries rather than attempt stocking (Le Clerc 1941).

One of the most well-known programs is the LIFE project in the *river Rhine*, during which Allis shad larvae from the Gironde-Garonne-Dordogne populations have been stocked in the Rhine. On average, the program has stocked 1.5–2 million larvae annually since 2008, in combination with some dam removals. By 2014, 57 juveniles and eight adults (87.5% of which were stocked individuals) were documented, marking the first evidence of natural reproduction in nearly a century (Hundt et al. 2015). This highlights that the potential for stocking to re-establish spawning populations is dependent on strong efforts in habitat restoration. However, this apparent success — evidenced by the occurrence

of natural reproduction — must be weighed against the still low number of returning adults and the low level of natural reproduction. Despite substantial stocking efforts, the number of returning adults remains low, suggesting that this program cannot yet be considered a success.

// 10.2.2 TWAITE SHAD

In the UK, the Twaite shad population inhabiting the *river Severn* benefited from stocking combined with improved water quality and fish passage installations. Juvenile releases helped to “kick-start” populations in rehabilitated habitats, though natural recolonization remains the primary driver of recovery (noa 2020, Hundt et al. 2015). Stocking, when paired with fish passes and gravel bed restoration, increased spawning success by 300% from 2010 to 2020. Successful stocking relies on suitable gravel substrates (0.5–1.5 m depth, 0.5–1.5 m/s flow) and adjacent deep pools for pre-spawning aggregation, which require habitat restoration measures (Maitland and Hatton-Ellis 2003). However, warming waters (exceeding 20° C) now threaten spawning sites, necessitating adaptive stocking into cooler tributaries.

// 10.2.3 AMERICAN SHAD AS AN EXAMPLE

Most research on shad stocking has been conducted in the USA on American shad (*Alosa sapidissima*) (Bailey and Zydlewski 2013, Cummins 2016, Potoka and Smith 2023, Quinn et al. 2024, Stevens et al. 1987). Similar to salmon, the Penobscot River in Maine is the focus of a stocking program aimed at improving population dynamics. In a study on this program, Bailey and Zydlewski (2013) clearly stated: “The decision about whether to stock a river system undergoing restoration should be made after evaluating the probability of natural recolonization and examining the costs and benefits of potentially accelerating recovery using a stocking program”, which supports the approach discussed for salmon. As with salmon, the lack of baseline data — particularly on population size and age structure — hampers robust evaluation of the program (Bailey and Zydlewski 2013). Nevertheless, their modeling work aimed to estimate the potential demographic effects of stocking prior to program initiation, as recommended for salmon. The program planned to stock 6–12 million larvae annually, reared from 500 to 1,200 adults, with a target goal of 633,300 spawners (Bailey and Zydlewski 2013). Despite the lack of initial data, they estimated that the efficiency of the stocking program would depend on the initial population size. They also found that supplementation may be ineffective even at low run sizes, and that stocking would only be beneficial when population size is below 10% of carrying capacity (Bailey and Zydlewski 2013). The authors suggest that shad stocking is a more appropriate tool for reintroduction than for supplementation (e.g., in a conservation context). They also concluded that, as for salmon, the decision to stock or not could be informed by a structured decision-making approach (Bailey and Zydlewski 2013).

Another extensive stocking program targets the Roanoke River in North Carolina (Potoka and Smith 2023). Despite significant hatchery releases, annual monitoring did not detect an increase in adult returns. For this population, stocking of genetically marked fry contributed 67% to the spawning stock, while natural recruitment remained low due to blocked migration routes and limited spawning habitat (Potoka and Smith 2023). This underscores the risk of creating hatchery-dependent populations without addressing habitat limitations. It also demonstrates that, from a conservation perspective, such

programs fail to restore a self-sustaining wild population relying on natural reproduction (Hasselman and Limburg 2012).

In another river, the Potomac, 22 million fry were stocked from 1995 to 2014, alongside the installation of fishways at Little Falls Dam. These actions led to a tenfold increase in adult returns (Cummins 2016). While the evaluation focused only on the number of returning adults, the authors stated that this recovery is a positive sign that investments in water quality improvements, habitat access, and fisheries management are effective (Cummins 2016). In contrast, the Rappahannock River did not show an increase in adult returns despite stocking 34 million fry from 2003 to 2014, mainly due to persistent migration barriers and offshore overfishing at the time of evaluation. Altogether, these examples illustrate the futility of stocking without concurrent habitat restoration and fisheries management.

10.3. CHALLENGES AND RISKS OF STOCKING

Stocking programs for shad species face significant challenges, with potential risks that may outweigh benefits if not carefully managed. As with salmon, most available evaluations are based only on the number of returning adults, which may initially increase after the start of a stocking program and then decrease thereafter (Hasselman and Limburg 2012, McGrath et al. 2022). For example, in the James River (Virginia), returns of American shad increased in 1998, five years after the start of a stocking program, reached a peak in 2003, and then declined (McGrath et al. 2022). In one of the best-studied programs on *Alosa sapidissima* (American shad), authors suggested that stocking programs may lead to a substitution of wild individuals by hatchery-reared shad, rather than an increase in natural recruitment (Aunins et al. 2014).

// 10.3.1 TECHNICAL PRACTICES AND HATCHERY EFFECTS

Some studies have directly investigated how hatchery-reared Allis shad differ from wild shad, as well as factors that can directly affect the success of stocking operations. Stoll and Beeck (2011) examined whether simple surface waves in rivers could lead to the stranding of stocked larvae and juveniles. Using hatchery-reared individuals provided by MIGADO, they found that up to 17% of stocked individuals died stranded within just seven hours after release. The stranding rate decreased with the age of stocked individuals but increased with sunny conditions and lower water temperatures (Stoll and Beeck 2011). These results indicate that the immediate efficiency of stocking operations can be directly impacted by river conditions and that even minor environmental variables, such as surface waves, may lead to the stranding of a significant proportion of stocked individuals.

In another study, authors investigated common malformations found in Allis shad juveniles (Wünnemann et al. 2017). Over several years of hatchery production monitoring, staff observed numerous individuals aged 1–2 months with malformations of the upper jaw. In a specific experiment analyzing 41 hatchery-reared Allis shad aged 2–6 months, all individuals exhibited cystic malformations on the upper jaw, which were not linked to infectious agents based on microbiological, virological, parasitological, and histological examinations (Wünnemann et al. 2017). The authors suggested these cystic

malformations, as well as other observed deformities, resulted from hatchery practices and represent a severe sign of impaired health and welfare in captive-reared Allis shad.

// 10.3.2 GENETIC RISKS

As with salmon, stocking with non-local broodstock can introduce maladapted alleles. For example, American shad stocked in the Roanoke River (Virginia) showed limited contributions to natural spawning stocks due to genetic mismatches, despite high initial survival rates. A study of the American shad stocking program in the James River, which used hatchery-reared shad from parents originating from the Pamunkey River, investigated genetic effects and found genetic differentiation between the two populations. The study also found the stocking program carried a risk of outbreeding depression (Aunins et al. 2014, Aunins 2010, Brown et al. 2000). Although shad populations generally exhibit less pronounced genetic structure than salmon, stocking programs may reduce genetic differentiation among populations (Aunins et al. 2014, Hasselman and Limburg 2012).

A further issue arises from the small broodstock pools often used in Allis shad programs. Indeed, broodstocks smaller than 20 individuals — as opposed to the higher numbers recommended for general broodstock management — may increase the risk of inbreeding and genetic drift (Milot et al. 2013). The Rhine reintroduction project used larvae from the Gironde population, but long-term monitoring is needed to assess genetic diversity retention.

// 10.3.3 DOMESTICATION AND FITNESS COSTS

In the Potomac River, stocked American shad fry had higher initial survival but lower marine survival compared to wild counterparts, suggesting that domestication selects for traits maladaptive in the wild (Cummins 2016). These questions still require further investigation, as there is a significant lack of knowledge to fully understand domestication and fitness costs in shad.

// 10.3.4 ECOLOGICAL DISRUPTION

In some American rivers, such as the Columbia River, the increased abundance of American shad (which is non-native in that system) coincided with declines in native Pacific salmon populations (Quinn et al. 2024). In a recent study examining the potential negative effects of shad stocking on salmon, authors did not find significant impacts but concluded that further investigations are warranted to understand ecological interactions with native fishes and to provide a clearer scientific basis for management decisions regarding shad stocking (Quinn et al. 2024).

// 10.3.5 CLIMATE CHANGE

Predictive models suggest that southern European habitats may become unsuitable for Allis shad by 2100 due to warming, while northern regions (e.g., Scotland) could become viable. Stocking efforts must therefore prioritize future climate-resilient habitats (OSPAR 2021).

10.4. RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the number of stocking programs for shads (Allis, American, or Twaite), it is surprising how few scientific studies have evaluated the consequences and efficiency of such programs, especially in light of the economic investments involved (Hasselman and Limburg 2012). Overall, a study investigating stocking programs in alosines concluded that current stocking practices are not consistent with the long-term persistence of wild, naturally reproducing, and genetically distinct shad populations (Hasselman and Limburg 2012). This is supported by the limited results available from stocking programs (Aunins et al. 2014, Bailey and Zydlewski 2013, Cummins 2016, McGrath et al. 2022). Therefore, all recommendations made for salmon should also be applied to shad, with even greater care and monitoring of programs to assess their outcomes, given the clear lack of available knowledge.

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CHAPTER **11**

Conclusion

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This synthesis distils more than a century of scientific research and field experience devoted to stocking Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and the closely related shad species (*Alosa alosa* and *A. fallax*). Stocking programs for Atlantic salmon and shad species (Allis shad and Twaite shad) have been widely implemented in Europe and North America as part of efforts to restore declining populations and support fisheries. Despite the significant resources invested, the overall effectiveness of these programs remains limited and uncertain in the long term, while the risks to wild populations remain high.

11.1. THE PROMISE AND THE REALITY OF STOCKING

In the immediate aftermath of industrialisation, stocking appeared almost magical: millions of juveniles were released into European and North American rivers, and early monitoring showed impressive returns of adults in the first spawning season. Yet, longitudinal studies eventually revealed a sobering pattern. While large-scale hatchery releases initially offered a rapid means of compensating for population declines, they also exposed the limits of purely cosmetic fixes in the face of complex ecological degradation. Initial pulses of returning fish seldom translated into self-sustaining wild populations. Indeed, while short-term increases in adult returns are sometimes observed, these gains rarely lead to sustainable, self-reproducing wild populations. The numerical boost faded after a few generations, and in many catchments, adult abundance slipped back to pre-stocking levels once supplemental releases ceased. This highlights the complexity of biological, ecological, and genetic factors influencing stocking outcomes and stresses the need to stop seeing stocking as a suitable action to compensate or mitigate other threats to salmon and shad populations.

The reasons for this short-lived success are multifaceted. Hatchery fish, even when produced from local broodstock, experience artificial conditions that relax or redirect natural selection. The resulting behavioural shifts — altered predator avoidance, modified homing precision, or simply reduced wariness — lower survival and diminish reproductive performance. Furthermore, the massive influx of juveniles can create density-dependent bottlenecks in nursery reaches, intensifying intra-specific

Figure 11.1: Conceptual scheme summarizing the key factors influencing the success and limitations of Atlantic salmon and shad stocking programs, highlighting genetic, ecological, and management considerations. ©C. Bouchard

competition and masking habitat limitations that would otherwise signal the need for environmental restoration.

Moreover, **conservation-oriented stocking** using local spawners in small populations **exacerbates demographic pressures** by *removing reproductive individuals* - precisely when populations are **at their most vulnerable** (i.e., at low abundance). This creates a “**conservation paradox**” where management actions **undermine the very populations** they aim to protect.

11.2. GENETIC CONSEQUENCES

Genetic integrity lies at the heart of long-term population resilience. One of the key insights from the reviewed literature is the crucial importance of local adaptation. Stocking campaigns conducted without rigorous genetic safeguards frequently erode allelic richness, reduce effective population size, and dilute micro-local adaptations.

Stocking with broodstock sourced from local populations helps preserve the genetic integrity and adaptive potential of the target populations. Conversely, the use of non-local or hatchery-adapted fish can lead to genetic introgression that dilutes locally adapted gene complexes, potentially reducing the fitness and resilience of wild populations. Even minimal introgression from hatchery lineages may impose fitness costs that persist long after the cessation of releases. This genetic homogenization is a significant risk, especially given the documented effects of domestication in hatchery environments, which select for traits maladaptive in the wild. Such domestication effects can reduce survival and reproductive success once stocked fish enter natural habitats.

Moreover, the genetic risks are compounded by the so-called Ryman-Laikre effect, where the effective population size may decline despite increased census numbers due to the disproportionate reproductive contribution of hatchery fish. This phenomenon threatens the long-term genetic diversity essential for population persistence under changing environmental conditions.

11.3. ECOLOGICAL CONTEXT, MONITORING, AND COSTS

Beyond genetics, the ecological context plays a decisive role in the success or failure of stocking programs. The restoration of habitat quality and connectivity emerges as a fundamental prerequisite. Without addressing barriers to migration, degraded spawning grounds, and water quality issues, stocking alone cannot compensate for the loss of natural reproductive capacity. Successful restoration cases consistently combine stocking with habitat restoration measures, underscoring that stocking should be viewed as a complementary tool to prime the pump rather than a standalone solution. In fact, most successful restoration programs are mainly due to natural recolonization by strayers from proximate populations.

From a technical standpoint, many programs suffer from a lack of rigorous monitoring and evaluation. Baseline data on population size, age structure, and genetic diversity are often missing prior to stocking, making it difficult to assess program effectiveness objectively. Furthermore, the absence of

clear, measurable objectives and adaptive management frameworks limits the ability to refine stocking strategies over time.

Economic considerations also weigh heavily on the viability of stocking programs. The costs associated with hatchery production, transport, and release are substantial, and without demonstrable long-term benefits, such investments may not represent the best use of limited conservation resources. This calls for comprehensive cost-benefit analyses integrated with ecological and genetic risk assessments before program implementation.

11.4. SHAD SPECIFICITIES

For shad species, the knowledge gaps are even more pronounced. Stocking programs for Allis and Twaite shad are less studied and documented compared to salmon, yet they face similar challenges. The limited number of broodstock used in some programs raises concerns about inbreeding and loss of genetic diversity. Moreover, the success of shad stocking appears tightly linked to concurrent habitat improvements, including the removal of migration barriers and enhancement of spawning habitats.

Finally, governance structures must support adaptive management, involving stakeholders at local and regional levels to ensure transparency, accountability, and responsiveness to new knowledge. Only through such integrated approaches can stocking contribute meaningfully to the recovery and long-term sustainability of Atlantic salmon and shad populations.

11.5. KNOWLEDGE GAPS AND RESEARCH PRIORITIES

Although the literature on salmonid stocking is vast, notable gaps persist. Long-term studies investigating effects such as genomic changes capable of distinguishing neutral from adaptive introgression remain scarce. Similarly, data on the combined effects of climate change and stocking on migratory phenology are almost entirely absent. For shad, the paucity of controlled experiments, particularly in European rivers, leaves many fundamental questions unresolved, from larval drift dynamics to the energetic costs of passage through fishways.

To address these gaps, future studies should integrate whole-river experimental designs — before/after, control/impact frameworks — coupled with individual-based tagging and modelling. Such designs would not only capture population-level responses but also quantify individual heterogeneity (i.e, diversity, the so-called tank for adaptation) and indirect ecosystem effects that traditional electrofishing surveys or monitoring of adult returns often overlook. Without conducting such studies, it is illusory to continue stocking programs from a conservation perspective.

11.6. CONDITIONS FOR SUCCESSFUL USE OF STOCKING

Despite these caveats, stocking retains a narrowly defined utility. It can help re-establish functional runs in systems where major obstacles to migration have been recently removed and all pressures are

managed, leaving a temporary demographic vacuum that natural recolonisation would fill only slowly.

Future stocking efforts must be carefully designed and integrated within broader conservation and management frameworks. Prioritizing habitat restoration and ensuring the use of genetically appropriate broodstock are essential. Stocking should be employed as a temporary measure with clearly defined goals and accompanied by robust scientific monitoring to evaluate demographic, genetic, and ecological outcomes. Crucially, these circumstances must be accompanied by a transparent, time-bounded exit strategy, as well as an adaptive management framework grounded in science. Managers should define quantitative thresholds beyond which supplemental stocking is phased out.

Overall, the cumulative evidence points toward a strategic realignment of restoration priorities:

1. **Prioritise habitat integrity.** Barrier removal, flow regulation, and water-quality improvements consistently deliver higher returns on investment than long-term hatchery support.
2. **Apply stocking as a temporary, adaptive measure.** Every program should include predefined success metrics and a sunset clause, ensuring that supplemental releases do not become an entrenched substitute for habitat repair.
3. **Safeguard genetic diversity.** Broodstock ought to mirror the donor population's full allelic spectrum, and hatchery protocols must minimize domestication selection by limiting captive residence and maintaining naturalised rearing environments.
4. **Monitor impacts.** A continuous scientific monitoring program should be set up to enable adaptive management.
5. **Monitor more than genetics.** Phenotypic traits, behaviour, life-history characteristics, and demographic parameters should all be monitored alongside genetic diversity.
6. **Expand participatory governance.** Transparent communication of objectives, methods, and costs fosters public trust and aligns expectations across anglers, conservationists, and regulatory agencies.

Stocking, once heralded as a panacea for dwindling fish runs, has matured into a management tool of last resort—valuable under specific, constrained circumstances, but incapable of compensating indefinitely for degraded habitats. Decades of empirical research converge on a consistent message: the future of Atlantic salmon and shad will hinge less on the volume of juveniles released and more on the rivers' capacity to sustain the natural life cycle. By treating stocking as a carefully monitored bridge to ecological recovery—rather than a perpetual crutch—managers can restore not only fish abundance but also the evolutionary processes and ecosystem services that make these migratory species irreplaceable.

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